

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Iterated multiple points I: Equations and pathologies

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Funding information

MCIN/AEI/10.13039/501100011033,
Grant/Award Number:
PGC2018-094889-B-I00; ERDF A way of
making Europe

Abstract

This is the first of a two-part work on Kleiman's iterated multiple point spaces. Here we show general properties of these spaces and solve the problem of finding their equations in the case of maps of any corank between complex manifolds. We also describe pathologies regarding dimension and lack of symmetry.

MSC 2020

32S20 (primary), 14Q15, 58K30 (secondary)

INTRODUCTION

The multiple point spaces of maps $f : X \rightarrow Y$ are a key tool in areas such as enumerative geometry [11–13, 15, 31, 32], the study of Thom polynomials [10, 27], the vanishing (co)homology of disentanglements [8, 9, 21, 30] and the study of finite determinacy of map-germs [1, 2, 16, 18, 25, 28, 29] but, despite their relevance, these spaces are not well understood. While it is clear that the multiple point spaces must contain the strict multiple points (that is, r -tuples (x^1, \dots, x^r) such that $f(x^i) = f(x^j)$ and $x^i \neq x^j$, for all $i \neq j$), there is no consensus about the best way to include diagonal points in order to get a reasonable structure.

There are several approaches to the definition of multiple point spaces, some based on deformations [25], on the Hilbert scheme [13] or on Fitting ideals [23]. The approaches on deformations and Fitting ideals require the map to be finite, thus require $\dim X \leq \dim Y$. Here we study the

more general approach of Kleiman’s *iterated multiple point spaces* [11], defined for any separated morphism of schemes $f : X \rightarrow Y$, regardless of the dimensions of X and Y and the finiteness of f .

The *double point space* of f is

$$K_2 = \text{Res}_{\Delta X}(X \times_Y X),$$

the residual space of the fibered product $X \times_Y X$ along the diagonal ΔX (see 1.1 for the definition of residual space). Composition of the structure map with the first projection gives a map $K_2 \rightarrow X$. Higher order *multiple point spaces* are defined iteratively: The triple point space K_3 is the double point space of $K_2 \rightarrow X$, and comes with a map $K_3 \rightarrow K_2$. The quadruple point space K_4 is the double point space of $K_3 \rightarrow K_2$, and so on.

If X and Y are smooth and f has only corank one singularities (that is, if f is curvilinear in Kleiman’s terminology), then K_r coincides with Mond’s multiple point space D^r , the subspace of X^r given by the vanishing of the iterated divided differences (see [20]). Since the number of equations is $(r - 1)p$, one deduces that K_r is a local complete intersection in X^r , whenever it has the *correct dimension* $rn - (r - 1)p$, with $n = \dim X$ and $p = \dim Y$ (see Definition 5.5). A remarkable theorem of Marar and Mond [16] states that a corank one map is stable if and only if all D^r are smooth of the correct dimension, and that a corank one map germ is finitely determined if and only if the spaces D^r whose correct dimension is positive are isolated complete intersection singularities of the correct dimension and the spaces D^r whose correct dimension is negative are confined to the origin.

The main difficulty with Kleiman’s construction is to find explicit equations for K_r in the presence of singularities of corank ≥ 2 . In this paper, we propose an alternative description of K_r , which solves this problem for maps between smooth spaces X and Y , allowing singularities of any corank. For any fixed X , the spaces K_r of the maps $f : X \rightarrow Y$ can be embedded as closed subspaces of a *universal multiple point space* $B_r = B_r(X)$. By definition, B_r is the multiple point space of the constant map $X \rightarrow *$ (observe that the definition of B_r requires using multiple point spaces of a non-finite maps). If X is smooth of dimension n , then B_r is smooth of dimension rn ; indeed, it is the blowup of $B_{r-1} \times_{B_{r-2}} B_{r-1}$ along ΔB_{r-1} . Our main result, Theorem 3.1, states that

$$K_r = b^{-1}(K_{r-1} \times_{K_{r-2}} K_{r-1}) : E,$$

where $b : B_r \rightarrow B_{r-1} \times_{B_{r-2}} B_{r-1}$ is the blowup map, E is the exceptional divisor and $Z : W$ stands for the zero locus of the quotient $I_Z : I_W$ of the defining ideal sheaves of two subspaces Z and W . The right-hand side of the previous equality is taken in [22] as the definition of K_r . This expression is easier to compute, but it hides the iteration principle, which is essential in many instances, and the equality requires for X and Y to be smooth.

From this result, we derive explicit local equations of K_r inside B_r , which are natural generalizations of the iterated divided differences in a convenient atlas of B_r . As in the corank one case, K_r is locally defined by $(r - 1)p$ equations in B_r , hence it is a local complete intersection whenever it has the correct dimension. We remark that for $r = 2$, our description of K_r coincides with Ronga’s double point space [33].

Lastly, Section 6 is devoted to pathologies exhibited by K_r when f is a finite map with singularities of corank ≥ 2 and r is big enough. The first pathology is that K_r always fails to have the correct dimension, even if f is stable. In particular, it must have components of different

dimensions, since it is dimensionally correct along the corank one points. Second, the image of K_r by f does not coincide, even set-theoretically, with the multiple point space in the target given by Fitting ideals, as defined by Mond and Pellikaan in [23]. The last pathology is the lack of symmetry of K_r with respect to permutations of coordinates. Even for triple points, the natural action of S_3 on X^3 cannot be lifted to K_3 . This anomaly comes from the choice of the projection in the iteration process. It appears that fixing these pathologies would require a totally different approach, which seems out of our reach at the present moment. For better exposition, some technical proofs are given in the Appendix.

In a forthcoming paper [26], the local properties of K_r and their relation to stability and finite determinacy of maps will be studied. On one hand, we will show that K_3 is smooth when f is stable and that it provides a desingularization of the multiple point space D^3 , which is always singular when f has singularities of corank ≥ 2 . The analogous result for K_2 was proven by Ronga in [33]. On the other hand, smoothness fails from quadruple points onwards for generically one-to-one maps of corank ≥ 2 . These pathologies will be used to give a simple criterion for finite determinacy within a wide range of dimensions, analogous to the Marar–Mond criterion for the corank one case [16].

Based on Sections 4 and 5, we have implemented a library in SINGULAR [3] to compute the generalized divided differences of any polynomial map $f : \mathbb{C}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{C}^p$, that is, local equations of K_r in the charts of the smooth space B_r . The library `IteratedMultiPoint.lib` is freely available (see [24]) and its usage is illustrated in Example 5.12. We think that the library will be a useful tool for anyone interested in working with examples.

The technical obstacles of higher corank have forced authors to restrict their work to singularities of corank one. However, the attention paid to higher corank singularities has been growing over the years. They are finding a place in works about finite determinacy [2, 17, 18, 21, 28, 29], enumerative geometry [5] as well as some other topics [6]. We hope that this work will clarify some aspects of the higher corank case.

Some of the results of this paper appear in a simplified form in the recent monograph about singularities of mappings [22].

1 | PRELIMINARIES

1.1 | Terminology

We use preimages and intersections as defined for any category that has fibered products (such as the arrow categories introduced before Definition 2.17). This is done by replacing the notion of subset by that of monomorphism. An intersection $X_1 \cap X_2$ inside \mathcal{X} is the fibered product of two monomorphisms $X_i \hookrightarrow \mathcal{X}$, and the preimage of $S \hookrightarrow Y$ by a morphism $f : X \rightarrow Y$ is the fibered product $X \times_Y S$.

From now on, an arrow $X \hookrightarrow Y$ between two complex spaces stands for a locally closed embedding of complex spaces (as opposed to just a monomorphism) and we will call it simply an embedding. This means that $X \hookrightarrow Y$ factors as the composition of an open and a closed embedding. In particular, any embedding (f, f^\sharp) is a monomorphism in the category of complex spaces and $f^\sharp : \mathcal{O}_Y \rightarrow f_*\mathcal{O}_X$ is an epimorphism of sheaves.

An ‘*’ symbol on a diagram stands for the complex manifold consisting of a single point.

Given two closed complex subspaces $X = V(I)$ and $Y = V(J)$ of a complex space Z , we write $X : Y = V(I : J) \subseteq Z$.

Given a holomorphic map $f : X \rightarrow Y$ between manifolds, the *corank* of f at $x \in X$ is

$$\text{corank } f_x = \dim_{\mathbb{C}}(\ker df_x).$$

This work is written in the category of complex spaces, but it can be adapted to the category of schemes with separated morphisms. Also, some results cited here are stated for schemes in their original sources.

1.2 | Residual spaces

Here we introduce some properties satisfied by residual spaces, and their relation to blowups. These two constructions are similar, the difference being that the symmetric algebra plays for residual spaces the role played by the Rees algebra for blowups. Proofs which we could not find in the literature are contained in the Appendix. Our definition of residual (complex) space is just an adaptation of Kleiman's definition of residual scheme. We refer to [11, Section 2] for more details about residual schemes. For the definition and basic properties of the symmetric algebra we refer to [4].

Definition 1.1. Given a closed complex subspace $W = V(I) \subseteq X$, the *residual space* of X along W is the relative homogeneous spectrum

$$\text{Res}_W X = \text{Proj}_X S(I),$$

where $S(I)$ stands for the symmetric algebra of I , regarded as an \mathcal{O}_X -module. The residual space comes equipped with a canonical proper morphism

$$\text{Res}_W X \xrightarrow{r} X.$$

The residual space $\text{Res}_W X$ can be described locally (on the base X) as follows: Given a point $x \in X$, since I is a coherent sheaf, we can choose an open neighborhood U of x where we have a presentation

$$\mathcal{O}_X(U)^q \xrightarrow{A} \mathcal{O}_X(U)^p \longrightarrow I(U) \longrightarrow 0,$$

for some $p \times q$ -matrix $A = (a_{ij})$ with entries in $\mathcal{O}_X(U)$. This induces a graded presentation

$$(\mathcal{O}_X(U)[t_1, \dots, t_p](-1))^q \xrightarrow{\hat{A}} \mathcal{O}_X(U)[t_1, \dots, t_p] \longrightarrow S(I(U)) \longrightarrow 0,$$

where $\hat{A} = (\hat{A}_1, \dots, \hat{A}_q)$ and the \hat{A}_i are the linear forms

$$\hat{A}_i = \sum_{j=1}^p a_{ij} t_j, \quad i = 1, \dots, q.$$

It follows that $r^{-1}(U)$ is isomorphic to the closed complex subspace of $U \times \mathbb{P}^{p-1}$ given by the vanishing of \hat{A}_i , with $i = 1, \dots, q$. Moreover, the restriction $r : r^{-1}(U) \rightarrow U$ can be identified with the projection onto the first component. It is obvious from this description that r is an isomorphism on $X \setminus W$.

Another relevant property is that $\text{Res}_W X = \text{Bl}_W X$ when W is regularly embedded in X (which also follows from Micali [19]). By definition, W is regularly embedded in X if I is locally generated by a regular sequence g_1, \dots, g_p . In this case, the \hat{A}_i correspond to the trivial relations between the g_j . We have $q = \binom{p}{2}$ and by replacing the subindex i by (j, k) , with $1 \leq j < k \leq p$,

$$\hat{A}_{jk} = g_k t_j - g_j t_k.$$

This agrees with the local description of the blowup $\text{Bl}_W X$ along a regularly embedded subspace W .

The local description also makes clear that, in general, computing a residual space amounts to computing the matrix A of syzygies. By contrast, the blowup is a more difficult object to deal with.

Proposition 1.2. *Given an embedding $X \hookrightarrow \mathcal{X}$ and a closed embedding $\mathcal{W} \hookrightarrow \mathcal{X}$, there is a unique embedding $\text{Res}_{\mathcal{W} \cap X} X \hookrightarrow \text{Res}_{\mathcal{W}} \mathcal{X}$, making the following diagram commutative:*

$$\begin{array}{ccc} \text{Res}_{\mathcal{W} \cap X} X & \hookrightarrow & \text{Res}_{\mathcal{W}} \mathcal{X} \\ \downarrow & & \downarrow \\ X & \hookrightarrow & \mathcal{X} \end{array}$$

This construction is functorial, in the sense that, given a composition $X \hookrightarrow X' \hookrightarrow \mathcal{X}$, the associated embedding $\text{Res}_{\mathcal{W} \cap X} X \hookrightarrow \text{Res}_{\mathcal{W}} \mathcal{X}$ is the composition $\text{Res}_{\mathcal{W} \cap X} X \hookrightarrow \text{Res}_{\mathcal{W} \cap X'} X' \hookrightarrow \text{Res}_{\mathcal{W}} \mathcal{X}$.

If the embedding $X \hookrightarrow \mathcal{X}$ is closed (or open), then so is the embedding $\text{Res}_{\mathcal{W} \cap X} X \hookrightarrow \text{Res}_{\mathcal{W}} \mathcal{X}$.

Proof. See Proof 1 in the Appendix. □

Proposition 1.3. *Given two closed embeddings $X_i \hookrightarrow \mathcal{X}$ and a closed embedding $\mathcal{W} \hookrightarrow X_2 \hookrightarrow \mathcal{X}$, let $W = \mathcal{W} \cap X_1$. Inside $\text{Res}_{\mathcal{W}} \mathcal{X}$, we have*

$$\text{Res}_W(X_1 \cap X_2) = \text{Res}_W X_1 \cap \text{Res}_W X_2.$$

Proof. See Proof 2 in the Appendix. □

The previous property is key to this work, and it does not hold if one replaces residual spaces by blowups. For example, taking

$$\mathcal{X} = \mathbb{C}^2, X_1 = V(y), X_2 = V(y - x^2) \text{ and } \mathcal{W} = V(x, y),$$

one obtains $\text{Bl}_W(X_1 \cap X_2) = \emptyset$, but $\text{Bl}_W X_1 \cap \text{Bl}_W X_2 \neq \emptyset$. This is the main reason why, in order for multiple point spaces to satisfy many desirable properties, they are defined by means of residual spaces rather than blowups.

Residual schemes and blowups are nevertheless very much related. The next result, due to Micali [19] (see also [11, Proposition 2.3.1]) is the main property relating both constructions.

We write

$$b : \text{Bl}_Y X \rightarrow X$$

for the blowup of X along Y .

Proposition 1.4. *Let $Y \subseteq X' \subseteq X$ be closed complex subspaces, with Y regularly embedded in X . Then $\text{Res}_Y X = \text{Bl}_Y X$ and the respective defining ideals satisfy $I_{\text{Res}_Y X'} I_{b^{-1}(Y)} = I_{b^{-1}(X')}$.*

Going back to the previous example, we obtain $\text{Res}_{\mathcal{W}}(X_i) = \text{Bl}_{\mathcal{W}}(X_i)$. In order not to contradict Proposition 1.3, the spaces $\text{Bl}_{\mathcal{W}}(X_1 \cap X_2)$ and $\text{Res}_{\mathcal{W}}(X_1 \cap X_2)$ must disagree, which is allowed by the fact that $\mathcal{W} = V(x, y)$ is not regularly embedded in the complex space $X_1 \cap X_2 = V(x^2, y)$.

Remark 1.5. Taking into account that $b^{-1}(Y)$ is a Cartier divisor, the previous property can be restated as follows: If Y is regularly embedded in X , then

$$\text{Res}_Y X' = b^{-1}(X') : b^{-1}(Y).$$

Observe that $b^{-1}(X')$ is the total transform of X' in $\text{Bl}_Y X$ but, in general, $\text{Res}_Y X'$ is not the strict transform. In fact, we see in Section 6 that $\text{Res}_Y X'$ may have greater dimension than X' .

We remark that some authors like Fulton [7, Definition 9.2.1] consider only the case where Y is a Cartier divisor in X and use the right-hand side of the above equality as a definition of residual scheme.

Lemma 1.6. *Let $X \hookrightarrow \mathcal{X}$ and let \mathcal{W} be a closed regularly embedded subspace of \mathcal{X} . If $\mathcal{W} \cap X$ is regularly embedded in \mathcal{X} , then*

$$\text{Res}_{\mathcal{W} \cap X} X = b_{\mathcal{W}}^{-1}(X) : b_{\mathcal{W}}^{-1}(\mathcal{W}) = b^{-1}(X) : b^{-1}(\mathcal{W} \cap X),$$

for the blowup maps $b_{\mathcal{W}} : \text{Bl}_{\mathcal{W}} \mathcal{X} \rightarrow \mathcal{X}$ and $b : \text{Bl}_{\mathcal{W} \cap X} \mathcal{X} \rightarrow \mathcal{X}$.

Proof. See Proof 3 in the Appendix. □

2 | THE MULTIPLE POINT SPACES K_r

Definition 2.1. Given a map $f : X \rightarrow Y$ between complex spaces, the *iterated multiple point spaces* K_r are defined as follows: Let $K_0 = Y$ and $K_1 = X$, so that f is a morphism $K_1 \rightarrow K_0$. For $r \geq 2$, we define

$$K_r = \text{Res}_{\Delta K_{r-1}} \left(K_{r-1} \times_{K_{r-2}} K_{r-1} \right)$$

and let $K_r \rightarrow K_{r-1}$ be the map obtained by composition of $K_r \rightarrow K_{r-1} \times_{K_{r-2}} K_{r-1}$ with the first projection $K_{r-1} \times_{K_{r-2}} K_{r-1} \rightarrow K_{r-1}$. In order to distinguish multiple point spaces of different maps, we sometimes write $K_r(f) = K_r$.

By construction, the multiple point spaces satisfy the *iteration principle*:

Proposition 2.2. *For any map between complex spaces, and any integers $r, r' \geq 0$ and $s, s' \geq 1$, such that $r + s = r' + s'$, the multiple points satisfy*

$$K_r(K_s \rightarrow K_{s-1}) = K_{r'}(K_{s'} \rightarrow K_{s'-1}).$$

Away from the preimage of the diagonal, the double point space K_2 is isomorphic to $X \times_Y X$, and measures the failure of injectivity of f . What goes on over the diagonal is a more delicate matter, specially if we allow X to be singular.

Proposition 2.3. *A morphism $X \rightarrow Y$ is a monomorphism if and only if $K_2 = \emptyset$. In this case, all higher K_r are also empty.*

Proof. A morphism $X \rightarrow Y$ is a monomorphism if and only if the mapping $\Delta X \hookrightarrow X \times_Y X$ is an isomorphism. In turn, this is equivalent to $\text{Res}_{\Delta X} X \times_Y X = \emptyset$. For $r > 2$, the space K_r is the double point space of $\emptyset = K_{r-1} \rightarrow K_{r-2}$. This is a monomorphism, hence $K_r = \emptyset$. \square

Computing double points directly from the definition is hard and, as a rule, each step of the iteration process makes the problem harder. What follows is an exception where each step is accomplished by blowing up a manifold along a closed submanifold.

Proposition 2.4. *If $f : X \rightarrow Y$ is a submersion between complex manifolds, then all K_r are smooth, all $K_r \rightarrow K_{r-1}$ are submersions, and*

$$K_r = \text{Bl}_{\Delta K_{r-1}} (K_{r-1} \times_{K_{r-2}} K_{r-1}).$$

Proof. By the iteration principle, it suffices to show the result for $r = 2$. Since f is a submersion, $\Delta X \subseteq X \times_Y X \subseteq X \times X$ are submanifolds and, by Proposition 1.4, $K_2 = \text{Res}_{\Delta X}(X \times_Y X) = \text{Bl}_{\Delta X}(X \times_Y X)$. One checks easily that $K_2 \rightarrow X$ is submersive. \square

The reader may be surprised that we care about multiple points of submersions. After all, multiple points have always been regarded as a tool for the study of finite and generically one-to-one maps. As we will see, submersions do play a role in the study of multiple points of general maps between manifolds.

Before being able to compute K_r for possibly non-submersive maps, we need to figure out certain relations between spaces $K_r = K_r(f)$ and $K'_r = K_r(f')$, in terms of relations satisfied by maps $f : X \rightarrow Y$ and $f' : X' \rightarrow Y'$. This is the starting point:

Proposition 2.5. *Every commutative diagram of the form*

$$\begin{array}{ccc} X & \longrightarrow & Y \\ \downarrow & & \downarrow \\ X' & \longrightarrow & Y' \end{array} \tag{D}$$

extends uniquely to a sequence of commutative diagrams

$$\begin{array}{ccccccc}
 \cdots & \longrightarrow & K_3 & \longrightarrow & K_2 & \longrightarrow & X & \longrightarrow & Y \\
 & & \downarrow & & \downarrow & & \downarrow & & \downarrow \\
 \cdots & \longrightarrow & K'_3 & \longrightarrow & K'_2 & \longrightarrow & X' & \longrightarrow & Y'
 \end{array}$$

satisfying the following properties:

(1) The embeddings $K_r \hookrightarrow K'_r$ form commutative diagrams

$$\begin{array}{ccc}
 K_r & \hookrightarrow & K'_r \\
 \downarrow & & \downarrow \\
 K_{r-1} \times_{K_{r-2}} K_{r-1} & \hookrightarrow & K'_{r-1} \times_{K'_{r-2}} K'_{r-1}
 \end{array}$$

(2) For any commutative diagram

$$\begin{array}{ccc}
 X & \longrightarrow & Y \\
 \downarrow & & \downarrow \\
 X' & \longrightarrow & Y' \\
 \downarrow & & \downarrow \\
 X\varepsilon & \longrightarrow & Y\varepsilon
 \end{array}$$

the embedding $K_r \hookrightarrow K''_r$ is the composition $K_r \hookrightarrow K'_r \hookrightarrow K''_r$.

(3) If $X \rightarrow X'$ is an isomorphism and $Y \rightarrow Y'$ is an embedding, then $K_r \hookrightarrow K'_r$ is an isomorphism.

Proof. By the iteration principle, it suffices to show the first step of the extension, because every square in the extended diagram is of the form (D). Notice that the embedding $X \times_Y X \hookrightarrow X' \times_{Y'} X'$ has ΔX as the preimage of $\Delta X'$. Moreover, the construction of this embedding is functorial in the same sense of Item 2, and gives an isomorphism if the hypotheses of Item 3 are met. Applying Proposition 1.2, we obtain the embedding $K_2 \hookrightarrow K'_2$, also in a functorial way. Therefore, the resulting embedding also satisfies Items 2 and 3. □

The simplest diagram (D) gives an interesting outcome: For a fixed space X , the multiple point spaces of all maps $X \rightarrow Y$ can be embedded into unique universal spaces.

Definition 2.6. The universal r -th multiple point space of a complex space X is

$$B_r = K_r(X \rightarrow *),$$

where $X \rightarrow *$ is the constant map. In order to distinguish the universal spaces of different complex spaces, we write $B_r(X) = B_r$.

Proposition 2.7. The universal multiple point spaces satisfy the following:

(1) For every map $f : X \rightarrow Y$, there is a canonical embedding

$$K_r \hookrightarrow B_r.$$

(2) For every embedding $X \hookrightarrow X'$, there is a canonical embedding

$$B_r(X) \hookrightarrow B_r(X').$$

The construction of B_r is functorial in the sense that the embeddings in Item 2 commute with compositions. The embeddings of Items 1 and 2 commute with the morphisms $K_r \rightarrow K_{r-1}$, $B_r \rightarrow B_{r-1}$ and $B'_r \rightarrow B'_{r-1}$, and they are compatible with the structure maps to the fibered products.

Proof. Extend, respectively, the following two diagrams:

$$\begin{array}{ccc} X & \longrightarrow & Y \\ \parallel & & \downarrow \\ X & \longrightarrow & * \end{array} \qquad \begin{array}{ccc} X & \longrightarrow & * \\ \downarrow & & \downarrow \\ X' & \longrightarrow & * \end{array} \qquad \square$$

Proposition 2.8. For the projection $T \times X \rightarrow T$, we have $K_r = T \times B_r(X)$, and $K_r \rightarrow K_{r-1}$ is the product of the identity $T \rightarrow T$ and $B_r(X) \rightarrow B_{r-1}(X)$.

Proof. Letting $B_r = B_r(X)$, the claim follows inductively from the isomorphisms $(T \times B_{r-1}) \times_{(T \times B_{r-2})} (T \times B_{r-1}) \cong T \times (B_{r-1} \times_{B_{r-2}} B_{r-1})$ and $\text{Res}_{T \times \Delta B_{r-1}} (T \times B_{r-1} \times_{B_{r-2}} B_{r-1}) \cong T \times \text{Res}_{\Delta B_{r-1}} (B_{r-1} \times_{B_{r-2}} B_{r-1})$. □

Proposition 2.9. The universal multiple point spaces of a complex manifold X are the blowups $B_r = \text{Bl}_{\Delta B_{r-1}} (B_{r-1} \times_{B_{r-2}} B_{r-1})$.

Proof. This is a particular case of Proposition 2.4, because $X \rightarrow *$ is a submersion. □

By abuse of notation, all these blowup maps are written as

$$b : B_r \rightarrow B_{r-1} \times_{B_{r-2}} B_{r-1}$$

and all their exceptional divisors as $E = b^{-1}(\Delta B_{r-1})$.

Example 2.10. The universal double point space of \mathbb{C}^n can be described, globally, as the set

$$B_2(\mathbb{C}^n) = \{(x, x', u) \in \mathbb{C}^n \times \mathbb{C}^n \times \mathbb{P}^{n-1} \mid u \wedge (x' - x) = 0\}.$$

Now consider a map $f : \mathbb{C}^n \rightarrow Y$, with Y a manifold. Once embedded in $B_2(\mathbb{C}^n)$, the double point space K_2 of f has a nice geometric interpretation, going back to work of Ronga [33].

Proposition 2.11. As a set, the space K_2 of a map $f : \mathbb{C}^n \rightarrow Y$ between manifolds consists of the following points:

- (1) *strict points* $(x, x', [x' - x])$, with $x \neq x'$ and $f(x) = f(x')$,
- (2) *diagonal points* (x, x, u) , with $u \in \mathbb{P}(\ker df_x)$.

Observe that functoriality plays an important role in the previous constructions. In a diagram of the form (D), the spaces K_r, B_r and K'_r are canonically embedded in B'_r ; but the functoriality of the involved constructions gives us more: Extending the horizontal arrows in the diagram

$$\begin{array}{ccc}
 & X & \longrightarrow Y \\
 & \cong \uparrow & \swarrow \downarrow \\
 X & \longrightarrow & * \\
 \downarrow & \cong \downarrow & \downarrow \\
 & X' & \longrightarrow * \\
 \downarrow & \cong \downarrow & \downarrow \\
 X' & \longrightarrow & *
 \end{array}$$

we obtain that the compositions $K_r \hookrightarrow B_r \hookrightarrow B'_r$ and $K_r \hookrightarrow K'_r \hookrightarrow B'_r$ are equal. By the universal property of the intersection of B_r and K'_r in B'_r , we obtain the following result:

Proposition 2.12. *For any diagram of the form (D), there is a unique embedding*

$$K_r \hookrightarrow K'_r \cap B_r,$$

compatible with the embeddings $K_r \hookrightarrow K'_r$ and $K_r \hookrightarrow B_r$.

Theorem 2.13. *For any commutative diagram of the form*

$$\begin{array}{ccc}
 X & \longrightarrow & Y \\
 \downarrow & & \downarrow \\
 X' & \longrightarrow & Y'
 \end{array}$$

the multiple points satisfy $K_r = K'_r \cap B_r$, the intersection being made in B'_r .

Proof. By the iteration principle Proposition 2.2, it suffices to prove the theorem in the case $r = 2$. Moreover, we know that $X \times_{Y'} X = X \times_Y X$, so we may assume $Y = Y'$ and consider the commutative diagram:

$$\begin{array}{ccc}
 X & \longrightarrow & Y \\
 \downarrow & \nearrow & \\
 X' & &
 \end{array}$$

The embedding $X \hookrightarrow X'$ factors as the composition of an open and a closed embedding. By Proposition 1.2 we can suppose that $X \hookrightarrow X'$ is either open or closed. But the case that $X \hookrightarrow X'$ is open is obvious from the definition, so we only need to consider the case that $X \hookrightarrow X'$ is closed.

Now we apply Proposition 1.3: Since $X \times_Y X = (X' \times_Y X') \cap (X \times X)$ and $\Delta X = \Delta X' \cap (X \times X)$, we have

$$\text{Res}_{\Delta X}(X \times_Y X) = \text{Res}_{\Delta X'}(X' \times_Y X') \cap \text{Res}_{\Delta X}(X \times X),$$

which gives $K_2 = K'_2 \cap B_2$, the intersection being made in B'_2 . □

Something that illustrates the usefulness of previous result is that it allows us to extend a result about mappings between complex manifolds to a result about mappings between complex spaces:

Proposition 2.14. *Given two maps $f_i : X \rightarrow Y_i, i = 1, 2$, let*

$$f = (f_1, f_2) : X \rightarrow Y_1 \times Y_2.$$

Inside B_r , we have

$$K_r(f) = K_r(f_1) \cap K_r(f_2).$$

Proof. In the case where X, Y_1 and Y_2 are complex manifolds, the statement follows immediately from Theorem 5.2. This theorem gives the generators of K_r in B_r explicitly, and it is clear that the generators of $K_r(f)$ are obtained by putting together those of $K_r(f_1)$ and $K_r(f_2)$ (see Remark 5.3). The proof will thus be complete only after Theorem 5.2 is proved; here we show how to reduce the general case to that of maps between complex manifolds.

Given a point $z \in B_r$, to prove the statement it suffices to find an open neighborhood W of z in B_r , such that

$$K_r(f) \cap W = K_r(f_1) \cap K_r(f_2) \cap W.$$

Let $x = (x^{(1)}, \dots, x^{(r)}) \in X^r$ be the image of z by the obvious map $B_r \rightarrow X^r$ (see Remark 4.5). Clearly, we can take an open neighborhood U of $\{x^{(1)}, \dots, x^{(r)}\}$ in X and an open neighborhood V_i of $f_i(\{x^{(1)}, \dots, x^{(r)}\})$ in Y_i , for $i = 1, 2$, such that

- (1) $f_i(U) \subseteq V_i$,
- (2) there are closed embeddings $U \hookrightarrow \mathcal{U}$ and $V_i \hookrightarrow \mathcal{V}_i$, where \mathcal{U} and \mathcal{V}_i are complex manifolds,
- (3) there are analytic extensions $F_i : \mathcal{U} \rightarrow \mathcal{V}_i$ of $f_i|_U : U \rightarrow V_i$.

Letting $\mathcal{V} = \mathcal{V}_1 \times \mathcal{V}_2$ and $F = (F_1, F_2)$, Theorem 5.2 implies that $K_r(F) = K_r(F_1) \cap K_r(F_2)$, as we mentioned before.

Take $W = B_r(U)$, which is embedded in $B_r(\mathcal{U})$ naturally, and can also be considered as an open subset of $B_r = B_r(X)$ containing z . Now consider the diagrams

$$\begin{array}{ccc} U & \xrightarrow{f|_U} & V \\ \downarrow & & \downarrow \\ X & \xrightarrow{f} & Y \end{array} \qquad \begin{array}{ccc} U & \xrightarrow{f|_U} & V \\ \downarrow & & \downarrow \\ \mathcal{U} & \xrightarrow{F} & \mathcal{V} \end{array}$$

and the analogous diagrams for f_1 and f_2 . Applying Theorem 2.13, we obtain the desired equality:

$$\begin{aligned} K_r(f) \cap W &= K_r(f|_U) \\ &= K_r(F) \cap W \\ &= K_r(F_1) \cap K_r(F_2) \cap W \\ &= K_r(f_1|_U) \cap K_r(f_2|_U) \\ &= K_r(f_1) \cap K_r(f_2) \cap W. \end{aligned}$$

□

The following result of Kleiman (see [11, Proposition 2.4]) can be recovered from our previous results.

Proposition 2.15. *For any map $F : T \times X \rightarrow T \times Y$ of the form $F(t, x) = (t, f_t(x))$, the following hold:*

- (1) $K_r(F) \subseteq T \times B_r(X)$.
- (2) $K_r(f_{t_0}) = K_r(F) \cap \{t = t_0\}$.

Proof. The first item follows by putting Propositions 2.8 and 2.14 together. For the second item, apply Theorem 2.13 to the diagram

$$\begin{array}{ccc} \{t_0\} \times X & \longrightarrow & \{t_0\} \times Y \\ \downarrow & & \downarrow \\ T \times X & \longrightarrow & T \times Y \end{array}$$

and observe that, once $K_r(F)$ is embedded in $T \times B_r(X)$, the intersection $K_r(F) \cap B_r(\{t_0\} \times X)$ is nothing but $K_r(F) \cap \{t = t_0\}$. □

Theorem 2.13 has less obvious applications than the previous ones. As an example, we sketch the computation of double points of reflection maps, introduced in [29].

Example 2.16. Let G be a reflection group acting on \mathbb{C}^n . The orbit map (or quotient map) of G is a polynomial map $\mathbb{C}^n \xrightarrow{\omega} \mathbb{C}^n$, taking a G -orbit to a point, that is, $\omega^{-1}(\omega(x)) = Gx$, for all $x \in \mathbb{C}^n$. A *reflection map* is a map $f : X \rightarrow \mathbb{C}^n$ forming a commutative diagram

$$\begin{array}{ccc} X & \xrightarrow{f} & \mathbb{C}^n \\ \downarrow h & & \uparrow \omega \\ \mathbb{C}^n & & \end{array}$$

for some embedding h .

As it turns out, some basic theory of reflection groups suffices to describe the double point space of the orbit map, which is a union of smooth components indexed by G . To be precise, the double points are the reduced space

$$K_2(\omega) = \bigcup_{g \in G \setminus \{1\}} B_g,$$

where each $B_g \subseteq B_2(\mathbb{C}^n)$ is obtained by blowing up the graph of the map $g : \mathbb{C}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{C}^n$ along $\Delta(\text{Fix } g)$.

The double point space $K_2(f)$ can be computed easily from $K_2(\omega)$, by Theorem 2.13, and it inherits the same G -indexed decomposition. This machinery was used to show the finite determinacy of new and very degenerate families of examples of map-germs $\mathbb{C}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{C}^{2n-1}$, for all n . For

instance, the maps

$$(x, y) \mapsto (x^a, y^b, (x + y)^p),$$

$$(x, y, z) \mapsto (x^a, y^b, z^c, (x + y + z)^p, (x - y + 2z)^q, (x + y - 2z)^r),$$

are \mathcal{A} -finitely determined if the integers a, b, c, p, q, r are pairwise coprime and p, q and r are odd.

As already noted, functoriality is key for our results. We finish this section by introducing a new layer of formalism, where the multiple point spaces are replaced by multiple point *functors*, and then giving reinterpretations of our results from this point of view.

The *arrow category* $A(C)$ of a category C has as objects the arrows of C , and as morphisms $f \rightarrow f'$ the commutative diagrams of the form

$$\begin{array}{ccc} X & \xrightarrow{f} & Y \\ \downarrow & & \downarrow \\ X' & \xrightarrow{g} & Y' \end{array}$$

which we simply call *squares*. The identity square and the composition of squares are defined in the obvious way. Now let C be the category of complex spaces. We write $A'(C)$ and $A''(C)$, respectively, for the wide subcategories of $A(C)$ (that is, subcategories including all objects but only some of the morphisms) whose squares are, respectively, of the forms

$$\begin{array}{ccc} X & \xrightarrow{f} & Y \\ \downarrow & & \downarrow \\ X' & \xrightarrow{f} & Y' \end{array} \quad \text{and} \quad \begin{array}{ccc} X & \xrightarrow{f} & Y \\ \downarrow & & \downarrow \\ X' & \xrightarrow{f} & Y' \end{array} .$$

Thanks to Proposition 2.5, we may disguise Kleiman’s multiple point spaces as functors.

Definition 2.17. The *double point functor* is

$$\mathbf{K}_2 : A'(C) \rightarrow A''(C),$$

taking a map $X \rightarrow Y$ to the map $\mathbf{K}_2 \rightarrow X$. At the level of morphisms, \mathbf{K}_2 is given by

$$\begin{array}{ccc} X & \longrightarrow & Y \\ \downarrow & & \downarrow \\ X' & \longrightarrow & Y' \end{array} \quad \longmapsto \quad \begin{array}{ccc} \mathbf{K}_2 & \longrightarrow & X \\ \downarrow & & \downarrow \\ \mathbf{K}'_2 & \longrightarrow & X' \end{array}$$

In accordance with the iteration principle, the *iterated multiple point functors* are defined as

$$\mathbf{K}_r = \mathbf{K}_2 \circ \dots \circ \mathbf{K}_2.$$

These functors give maps $\mathbf{K}_r f \in \text{Hom}(K_r, K_{r-1})$, for any map $f : X \rightarrow Y$. To be consistent with the convention that $K_1 = X$ and $K_0 = Y$, the functor \mathbf{K}_1 is set to be the identity $A'(C) \rightarrow A'(C)$.

Now that we have turned multiple point spaces into functors, we shall revisit the results obtained so far. From the fact that complex spaces have fibered products, it follows easily that $A(C), A'(C)$ and $A''(C)$ have them as well. Indeed, the fibered product $f_1 \times_F f_2$ of two arrows $f_i : X_i \rightarrow Y_i$, each equipped with a square to $F : \mathcal{X} \rightarrow \mathcal{Y}$, is the canonical arrow

$$X_1 \times_{\mathcal{X}} X_2 \rightarrow Y_1 \times_{\mathcal{Y}} Y_2,$$

equipped with the two squares forming the top and left faces of the commutative cubical diagram

satisfying the usual universal property of fibered products. We call such a diagram a *cartesian cube*. Now Theorem 2.13 and Proposition 2.14 can be rephrased as the fact that, for cartesian cubes of the forms

the multiple point functors commute with fibered products. In other words, given a diagram of any of the two forms above, we have that

$$\mathbf{K}_r f_1 \times_{\mathbf{K}_r F} \mathbf{K}_r f_2 = \mathbf{K}_r (f_1 \times_F f_2).$$

However, at this point we do not have a proof or a counterexample to the fact that \mathbf{K}_r commutes with general fibered products.

3 | A FORMULA FOR K_r INSIDE B_r

We give an explicit expression for K_r , embedded in B_r , in the case where X is a complex manifold. This will lead us to the formulas for K_r from Section 5.

For any $r \geq 2$, we may assume inductively that we have embedded K_{r-1} in B_{r-1} and that we have a map $K_{r-2} \rightarrow B_{r-2}$ (for the initial case of $r = 2$, we take the identity map $X \rightarrow X$ and $Y \rightarrow *$). This induces an embedding

$$K_{r-1} \times_{K_{r-2}} K_{r-1} \hookrightarrow B_{r-1} \times_{B_{r-2}} B_{r-1}.$$

Recall that we write $b : B_r \rightarrow B_{r-1} \times_{B_{r-2}} B_{r-1}$ for the blowup maps, and E for their exceptional divisors.

Theorem 3.1. *For any map $f : X \rightarrow Y$ between manifolds and any $r \geq 2$,*

$$K_r = b^{-1}(K_{r-1} \times_{K_{r-2}} K_{r-1}) : E.$$

Proof. We write $M_r = b^{-1}(K_{r-1} \times_{K_{r-2}} K_{r-1}) : E$ and show $M_r = K_r$ in three steps.

Step 1: We show the property analogous to Theorem 2.13 for M_r . For any commutative diagram of maps between manifolds

we have $M_r = M'_r \cap B_r$. In other words, $M_r = h^{-1}(M'_r)$, for the embedding $B_r \hookrightarrow B'_r$ canonically induced by $X \hookrightarrow X'$.

We proceed by induction on r . Set $M_0 = M'_0 = Y$, $M_1 = X$ and $M'_1 = X'$, so that the cases $r = 0, 1$ are trivial. By induction, we may assume that $r \geq 2$ and that the statement holds up to $r - 1$. Consider the commutative diagram

$$\begin{array}{ccc}
 B_r & \xrightarrow{h} & B'_r \\
 \downarrow b & & \downarrow b \\
 (B_{r-1}/B_{r-2})^2 & \xrightarrow{\bar{h}} & (B'_{r-1}/B'_{r-2})^2
 \end{array}$$

and, for convenience, write $\bar{M} = (M_{r-1}/M_{r-2})^2$ and $\bar{M}' = (M'_{r-1}/M'_{r-2})^2$.

We claim that $b^{-1}(\bar{M}) = h^{-1}(b'^{-1}(\bar{M}'))$. Indeed, by induction we have

$$\bar{M} = (h^{-1}(M'_{r-1})/h^{-1}(M'_{r-2}))^2 = (\bar{h})^{-1}(\bar{M}'),$$

and the claim follows from the commutativity $\bar{h} \circ b = b' \circ h$.

Let E and E' be the exceptional divisors on B_r and B'_r , and observe that $E = h^{-1}(E')$. We have the two equalities

$$M_r = h^{-1}(b'^{-1}(\bar{M}')) : h^{-1}(E'),$$

$$h^{-1}(M'_r) = h^{-1}(b'^{-1}(\bar{M}')) : E'.$$

Therefore, it suffices to show

$$h^{-1}(b'^{-1}(\bar{M}')) : h^{-1}(E') = h^{-1}(b'^{-1}(\bar{M}')) : E'.$$

In turn, this equality may be rewritten as

$$(b'^{-1}(\bar{M}') \cap B_r) : (E' \cap B_r) = ((b'^{-1}(\bar{M}')) : E') \cap B_r.$$

Now write $p : B'_r \rightarrow B'_{r-1}$ for the usual map, $pr_1 : (B'_{r-1}/B'_{r-1})^2 \rightarrow B'_{r-1}$ for the first projection and let

$$Z = p^{-1}(M'_{r-1}).$$

From the inclusion $p(b'^{-1}(\overline{M'})) = (pr_1 \circ b')(b'^{-1}(\overline{M'})) \subseteq M'_{r-1}$, we obtain $b'^{-1}(\overline{M'}) \subseteq Z$. Consequently, both sides of the equality we need to check are subspaces of Z , and the equality may be restated as

$$(J + S) : (I + S) = (J : I) + S,$$

for the ideal sheaves J, S and I defining $b'^{-1}(\Gamma')$, $B_r \cap Z$ and $E' \cap Z$ in Z , respectively.

The right to left inclusion holds in general, so we are left with the inclusion $(J + S) : (I + S) \subseteq (J : I) + S$. Now $\Delta B'_{r-1} \cap pr^{-1}(M'_{r-1}) = \Delta M'_{r-1}$ is a complex subspace of $\overline{M'}$, and, applying b'^{-1} , it follows that $E' \cap Z$ is a complex subspace of $b'^{-1}(\overline{M'})$ or, equivalently, that $J \subseteq I$. Moreover, the ideal I is principal, because E' is the exceptional divisor in B'_r , so locally we may write $I = \langle \lambda \rangle$.

Now let $a \in (J + S) : (I + S) = (J + S) : \lambda$. We have $\lambda a = j + s$, with $j \in J$ and $s \in S$. Since $J \subseteq I$, then $s = c\lambda$, for some c . Since B_r is smooth and is not contained in the exceptional divisor, we have $S : \lambda = S$, and hence $c \in S$. We have $\lambda(a - c) = j \in J$, so $a - c \in J : \lambda$, and therefore $a \in (J : \lambda) + S$.

Step 2: We reduce the proof to showing $K_r = M_r$ for submersions. For any map $X \rightarrow Y$ between manifolds, consider the commutative diagram

where Γ is the graph embedding and π the projection on the second factor. The embedding Γ induces embeddings $B_r(X) \hookrightarrow B_r(X \times Y)$, and π is obviously a submersion. Assuming that $K_r = M_r$ for submersions, from Theorem 2.13 and the previous step we obtain the equality

$$K_r(f) = K_r(\pi) \cap B_r(X) = M_r(\pi) \cap B_r(X) = M_r(f)$$

inside $B_r(X \times Y)$, as desired.

Step 3: We show $M_r = K_r$ for submersions. By induction, we may assume $M_{r-1} = K_{r-1}$ and $M_{r-2} = K_{r-2}$. We know from Proposition 2.4 that all maps $K_r \rightarrow K_{r-1}$ are submersions between smooth spaces. This in turn implies the smoothness of

$$Y = \Delta B_{r-1}, \quad Z = M_{r-1} \times_{M_{r-2}} M_{r-1} \quad \text{and} \quad X = B_{r-1} \times_{B_{r-2}} B_{r-1}.$$

Since submanifolds are regularly embedded, from Lemma 1.6 we obtain

$$\begin{aligned}
 M_r &= b^{-1} \left(M_{r-1} \times_{M_{r-2}} M_{r-1} \right) : b^{-1}(\Delta B_{r-1}) \\
 &= \text{Res}_{\Delta M_{r-1}} \left(M_{r-1} \times_{M_{r-2}} M_{r-1} \right) = K_r.
 \end{aligned}$$

□

Remark 3.2. Theorem 3.1 was already known for $r = 2$, that is, for double points of maps between smooth spaces, see, for example, [7, Section 9.3]. However, unlike other results found here, this one does not admit an easy reduction to the case $r = 2$. Observe that the source and target of higher maps $K_r \rightarrow K_{r-1}$ may not be smooth, and that we do not know a priori that $M_r = b^{-1}(K_{r-1} \times_{K_{r-2}} K_{r-1}) : E$ satisfies any sort of iteration principle. In general, arguments about the algebraic structure of higher K_r are delicate, and it is apparent that our proof relies heavily on the machinery from previous sections.

4 | COORDINATES FOR THE UNIVERSAL SPACES B_r

We give coordinates for $B_r(X)$ in the case where X is a complex manifold. First, we justify that it suffices to give coordinates for the spaces $B_r(\mathbb{C}^n)$

Definition 4.1. Let \mathcal{P} be a partition $r_1 + \dots + r_s = r$ of r . We say that a point $z \in B_r$ is of type \mathcal{P} if the components of its projection in X^r consist of s different points $x^{(i)} \in X$, each repeated r_s times (in a possibly disordered way).

Given a point $z \in B_r$ of type \mathcal{P} , we may take pairwise disjoint open subsets $U_1, \dots, U_s \subseteq X$, so that $x^{(i)} \in U_i$. For brevity, we write $f^{(i)} = f|_{U_i}$.

Proposition 4.2. Let $f : X \rightarrow Y$ be a map between complex manifolds. Around a point $z \in B_r$ of type \mathcal{P} , the space $K_r(f)$ is locally isomorphic to

$$K_{r_1}(f^{(1)}) \times_Y \dots \times_Y K_{r_s}(f^{(s)}).$$

Proof. See Proof 4 in the Appendix. □

Remark 4.3. Let $z \in B_r$ be a point of type \mathcal{P} as above, for a manifold X . Then B_r is locally isomorphic at z to

$$B_{r_1}(U_1) \times \dots \times B_{r_s}(U_s),$$

for some disjoint coordinate open subsets U_α , which we may regard them as subsets $U_\alpha \subset \mathbb{C}^n$. Since both U_α and \mathbb{C}^n are smooth of the same dimension, it follows from Propositions 2.9 and 2.7 that $B_r(U_\alpha)$ is an open submanifold of $B_r(\mathbb{C}^n)$. Hence, coordinates for $B_r(U_\alpha)$ are obtained by restriction of the coordinates for $B_r(\mathbb{C}^n)$.

4.1 | A pyramid of maps

We need one last ingredient, the triangular diagram below, before giving coordinates for the spaces B_r . We write the s -fold fibered product of a map $X \rightarrow Y$ as

$$(X/Y)^s = X \times_Y \dots \times_Y X.$$

Unless otherwise stated, maps $(X/Y)^s \rightarrow (X/Y)^{s-t}$ are assumed to drop the last t components. To avoid confusion, we write

$$(X/Y)^s \xrightarrow{\beta} X$$

for the map which keeps the last component and write $\tau : K_{r+1} \rightarrow K_r$ for the composition $K_{r+1} \xrightarrow{\beta} K_r \times_{K_{r-1}} K_r \xrightarrow{\beta} K_r$.

Lemma 4.4. *For any $X \rightarrow Y$, there are unique maps*

$$(K_{r+1}/K_r)^s \rightarrow (K_r/K_{r-1})^{s+1},$$

such that the following two diagrams commute:

$$\begin{array}{ccccccc}
 \dots & \longrightarrow & K_4 & & & & \\
 & & \downarrow & & & & \\
 \dots & \rightarrow & (K_3/K_2)^2 & \longrightarrow & K_3 & & \\
 & & \downarrow & & \downarrow & & \\
 \dots & \rightarrow & (K_2/X)^3 & \rightarrow & (K_2/X)^2 & \longrightarrow & K_2 \\
 & & \downarrow & & \downarrow & & \downarrow \\
 \dots & \rightarrow & (X/Y)^4 & \rightarrow & (X/Y)^3 & \rightarrow & (X/Y)^2 \rightarrow X
 \end{array} \tag{T_K}$$

where $K_{r+1} \rightarrow (K_r/K_{r-1})^2$ are the structure maps, and

$$\begin{array}{ccc}
 (K_{r+1}/K_r)^s & \rightarrow & (K_r/K_{r-1})^{s+1} \\
 \beta \downarrow & & \downarrow \beta \\
 K_{r+1} & \xrightarrow{\tau} & K_r
 \end{array}$$

Proof. See Proof 5 in the Appendix. □

Remark 4.5. As a particular case of Lemma 4.4, for any complex space X there is a unique analogous commutative diagram

$$\begin{array}{ccccccc}
 \dots & \longrightarrow & B_4 & & & & \\
 & & \downarrow & & & & \\
 \dots & \rightarrow & (B_3/B_2)^2 & \longrightarrow & B_3 & & \\
 & & \downarrow & & \downarrow & & \\
 \dots & \rightarrow & (B_2/X)^3 & \rightarrow & (B_2/X)^2 & \rightarrow & B_2 \\
 & & \downarrow & & \downarrow & & \downarrow \\
 \dots & \longrightarrow & X^4 & \longrightarrow & X^3 & \longrightarrow & X^2 \rightarrow X
 \end{array} \tag{T_B}$$

Now we are ready to give coordinates for $B_r = B_r(\mathbb{C}^n)$. For technical reasons, we need to describe the spaces $(B_r/B_{r-1})^s$ in the diagram (T_B) and the maps between them. To gain

intuition, we start with the universal double and triple points for \mathbb{C}^2 . This will also fix the notation for double and triple points of maps corank ≤ 2 , as in Examples 5.4 and 5.12.

4.2 | Atlas for the universal double point space $B_2(\mathbb{C}^2)$

Let $X = \mathbb{C}^2$. As stated in Example 2.10, the universal double point space of X is

$$B_2 = \{((x, y), (x', y'), (u_1 : u_2)) \in \mathbb{C}^2 \times \mathbb{C}^2 \times \mathbb{P}^1 \mid (x' - x, y' - y) \wedge (u_1, u_2) = 0\}.$$

The space B_2 is covered by the open subsets U_1, U_2 , where

$$U_i = \{((x, y), (x', y'), (u_1 : u_2)) \in B_2 \mid u_i \neq 0\}.$$

These open subsets are isomorphic to \mathbb{C}^4 , respectively, via the maps

$$\begin{aligned} ((x, y), (x', y'), (u_1 : u_2)) &\longmapsto \left((x, y), x' - x, \frac{u_2}{u_1} \right), \\ ((x, y), (x', y'), (u_1 : u_2)) &\longmapsto \left((x, y), y' - y, \frac{u_1}{u_2} \right). \end{aligned}$$

Finally, the inverse maps are

$$\begin{aligned} ((x, y), \lambda, a) &\longmapsto ((x, y), (x + \lambda, y + \lambda a), (1 : a)), \\ ((x, y), \lambda, a) &\longmapsto ((x, y), (x + \lambda a, y + \lambda), (a : 1)), \end{aligned}$$

and the exceptional divisor is given by $\lambda = 0$ on each U_i .

4.3 | Compatible atlas for $B_3(\mathbb{C}^2)$, $(B_2(\mathbb{C}^2)/\mathbb{C}^2)^2$ and $B_2(\mathbb{C}^2)$

By Proposition 2.9, B_3 is the blowup of $(B_2/\mathbb{C}^2)^2$ along ΔB^2 , and $(B_2/\mathbb{C}^2)^2$ can be seen as the space of tuples

$$((x, y), (x', y'), (x'', y''), [u], [u']) \in (\mathbb{C}^2)^3 \times (\mathbb{P}^1)^2,$$

such that

$$(x' - x, y' - y) \wedge u = (x'' - x, y'' - y) \wedge u' = 0.$$

By unicity of the maps in Lemma 4.4, the map $(B^2)^2 \rightarrow (\mathbb{C}^2)^3$ is given by

$$((x, y), (x', y'), (x'', y''), [u], [u']) \mapsto ((x, y), (x', y'), (x'', y'')),$$

because it satisfies the corresponding commutativities.

Now we cover $(B_2/\mathbb{C}^2)^2$ and B_2 by open coordinate subsets in a way that allows us to compute B_3 , and to express the maps $B^3 \rightarrow (B^2/\mathbb{C}^2)^2$ and $(B^2/\mathbb{C}^2)^2 \rightarrow (\mathbb{C}^2)^3$ conveniently. It is easy to see (and it follows from Lemma 4.7) that, by setting $L_1(x, y) = x$, $L_2(x, y) = y$ and $L_3(x, y) = x + y$, we have a covering of $(B_2/\mathbb{C}^2)^2$ by the three open subsets

$$U_i^2 = \{((x, y), (x', y'), (x'', y''), [u], [u']) \in (B_2/\mathbb{C}^2)^2 \mid L_i(u) \neq 0 \neq L_i(u')\}.$$

It is clear that $(B_2/\mathbb{C}^2)^2 \rightarrow B_2$ restricts to $U_1^2 \rightarrow U_1$ and $U_2^2 \rightarrow U_2$, so we shall add to our covering of B_2 a new open subset

$$U_3 = \{((x, y), (x', y'), [u]) \in B_2 \mid L_3(u) \neq 0\},$$

to have the corresponding restriction $U_3^2 \rightarrow U_3$. The isomorphism $U_3 \rightarrow \mathbb{C}^4$ and its inverse are given by

$$\begin{aligned} ((x, y), (x', y'), [u]) &\longmapsto \left((x, y), \left(x' - x + y' - y, \frac{u_1}{u_1 + u_2} \right) \right), \\ ((x, y), (\lambda, a)) &\longmapsto ((x, y), (x + \lambda a, y + \lambda(a - 1)), (a : a - 1)). \end{aligned}$$

To give coordinates to the new open subsets, fix some other linear forms L'_i , each of them linearly independent to the corresponding L_i , for example, $L'_1 = y$, $L'_2 = x$ and $L'_3 = x$. We have the isomorphisms $U_i^2 \rightarrow \mathbb{C}^6$ mapping a point $((x, y), (x', y'), (x'', y''), [u], [u'])$ to the point

$$\left((x, y), \left(L_i(x' - x, y' - y), \frac{L'_i(u)}{L_i(u)} \right), \left(L_i(x'' - x, y'' - y), \frac{L'_i(u')}{L_i(u')} \right) \right).$$

Our choices for $i = 1, 2, 3$ map the point $((x, y), (x', y'), (x'', y''), [u], [u'])$, respectively, to the point

$$\begin{aligned} &\left((x, y), \left(x' - x, \frac{u_2}{u_1} \right), \left(x'' - x, \frac{u'_2}{u'_1} \right) \right), \\ &\left((x, y), \left(y' - y, \frac{u_1}{u_2} \right), \left(y'' - y, \frac{u'_1}{u'_2} \right) \right), \\ &\left((x, y), \left(x' - x + y' - y, \frac{u_1}{u_1 + u_2} \right), \left(x'' - x + y'' - y, \frac{u'_1}{u'_1 + u'_2} \right) \right). \end{aligned}$$

The inverse isomorphisms $\mathbb{C}^6 \rightarrow U_i^2$ map a point $((x, y), (\lambda, a), (\lambda', a'))$, respectively, to the point

$$((x, y), (x + \lambda, y + \lambda a), (x + \lambda', y + \lambda' a'), (1 : a), (1 : a')),$$

$$((x, y), (x + \lambda a, y + \lambda), (x + \lambda' a', y + \lambda'), (a : 1), (a' : 1)),$$

$$((x, y), (x + \lambda a, y + \lambda(a - 1)), (x + \lambda' a', y + \lambda'(a' - 1)), (a : a - 1), (a' : a' - 1)).$$

To compute B_3 , observe that on each U_i^2 the diagonal ΔB^2 is regularly embedded by the equations

$$L_i(x', y') = L_i(x'', y''), \quad \frac{L'_i(u)}{L_i(u)} = \frac{L'_i(u')}{L_i(u')},$$

and is mapped to the set $\{\lambda = \lambda', a = a'\}$. Consequently, B_3 can be described as the set of tuples

$$((x, y), (x', y'), (x'', y''), [u], [u'], [v]),$$

satisfying the conditions

- (1) $((x, y), (x', y'), (x'', y''), [u], [u']) \in U_i$, for some i , with $1 \leq i \leq 3$,
- (2) $(L_i(x'' - x', y'' - y'), \frac{L'_i(u)}{L_i(u)} - \frac{L'_i(u')}{L_i(u')}) \wedge v = 0$.

We may cover B_3 by six open subsets U_{ij} , with $1 \leq i \leq 3$ and $1 \leq j \leq 2$, of the form

$$U_{ij} = \{((x, y), (x', y'), (x'', y''), [u], [u'], [v]) \in B_3 \mid L_i(u), L_i(u'), L_j(v) \neq 0\}.$$

The previous local isomorphisms allow us to regard B_3 on each U_{ij} as the set of tuples

$$((x, y), (\lambda, a), (\lambda', a'), [v]),$$

satisfying $L_j(v) \neq 0$ and $(\lambda' - \lambda, a' - a) \wedge v = 0$. Each U_{ij} is mapped isomorphically to \mathbb{C}^6 by means of

$$((x, y), (\lambda, a), (\lambda', a'), [v]) \mapsto \left((x, y), (\lambda, a), L_j(\lambda' - \lambda, a' - a), \frac{L'_j(v)}{L_j(v)} \right).$$

Our choices for $j = 1, 2$ map a point $((x, y), (\lambda, a), (\lambda', a'), [v])$, respectively, to the point

$$\begin{aligned} & \left((x, y), (\lambda, a), \lambda' - \lambda, \frac{v_2}{v_1} \right), \\ & \left((x, y), (\lambda, a), a' - a, \frac{v_1}{v_2} \right), \end{aligned}$$

The respective inverse isomorphisms map a point $((x, y), (\lambda, a), (\mu, b))$ to the point

$$\begin{aligned} & ((x, y), (\lambda, a), (\lambda + \mu, a + \mu b), (1 : b)), \\ & ((x, y), (\lambda, a), (\lambda + \mu b, a + \mu), (b : 1)). \end{aligned}$$

The exceptional divisor in B_3 is the preimage of the diagonal ΔB_2 by $B_3 \rightarrow (B_2/\mathbb{C}^2)^2$, and is given in U_{ij} by the equation $\mu = 0$.

Fixed i and j , we can arrange the coordinates $(x, y), (x', y'), (x'', y''), (\lambda, a), (\lambda', a')$ and (μ, b) of the spaces $\mathbb{C}^2, (\mathbb{C}^2)^2, B_2, (\mathbb{C}^2)^3, (B_2/\mathbb{C}^2)^2$ and B_3 into a triangle

$$\begin{array}{ccc} (\mu, b) & & \\ (\lambda', a') & (\lambda, a) & \\ (x'', y'') & (x', y') & (x, y) \end{array}$$

corresponding to the triangular diagram in Lemma 4.4. The expression in local coordinates of the maps $B_2 \rightarrow (\mathbb{C}^2)^2$, $B_3 \rightarrow (B_2/\mathbb{C}^2)^2$ and $(B^2/\mathbb{C}^2)^2 \rightarrow (\mathbb{C}^2)^3$ can be read directly from the maps $\mathbb{C}^4 \rightarrow U_i$, $\mathbb{C}^6 \rightarrow \tilde{U}_i$ and $\mathbb{C}^6 \rightarrow U_{ij}$. For example, for $\alpha = (i, j) = (1, 1)$, these maps are determined by

$$\begin{aligned} x' &= x + \lambda, & y' &= y + \lambda a, & x'' &= x + \lambda', & y'' &= y + \lambda' a' \\ \lambda' &= \lambda + \mu, & a' &= a + \mu b. \end{aligned}$$

4.4 | The general case: Atlas for $(B_r/B_{r-1})^s$, for $X = \mathbb{C}^n$

For the remaining of the section, we fix $X = \mathbb{C}^n$ and an integer $\ell \geq 2$. We give coordinate coverings of the spaces

$$(B_r/B_{r-1})^s, \text{ with } r + s \leq \ell + 1.$$

These are the spaces in a triangular diagram of the form (T_B) of Remark 4.5, having B_ℓ on the top. Our coverings are such that the maps

$$(B_{r+1}/B_r)^s \rightarrow (B_r/B_{r-1})^{s+1} \quad \text{and} \quad (B_r/B_{r-1})^s \rightarrow (B_r/B_{r-1})^{s-1}$$

take an open subset to an open subset. We are mostly interested in $B_r = (B_r/B_{r-1})^1$, but the spaces $(B_r/B_{r-1})^s$ with $s \geq 2$ are needed for the construction. The reader may convince themselves of this by inspecting the proof of Proposition 4.11.

Definition 4.6. We say that a collection of linear forms

$$\mathcal{L} = \{L_i : \mathbb{C}^{n+1} \rightarrow \mathbb{C}\}_{i=1}^m$$

is a *covering collection* for $(\mathbb{P}^n)^k$ if

- (1) $m \geq kn + 1$,
- (2) any $n + 1$ elements in \mathcal{L} are linearly independent.

Lemma 4.7. *If \mathcal{L} is a covering collection for $(\mathbb{P}^n)^k$, then the subsets*

$$V_L = \{(u^{(1)}, \dots, u^{(k)}) \in (\mathbb{P}^n)^k \mid L(u^{(i)}) \neq 0, \text{ for all } i \leq k\},$$

with $L \in \mathcal{L}$, form an open covering of $(\mathbb{P}^n)^k$.

Proof. Assume that some point $(u^{(1)}, \dots, u^{(k)}) \in (\mathbb{P}^n)^k$ is not contained in any V_L , that is, for every $L \in \mathcal{L}$, there is some $i \leq k$, such that $L(u^{(i)}) = 0$. Letting $\mathcal{L}_i = \{L \in \mathcal{L} \mid L(u^{(i)}) = 0\}$, we have that $\mathcal{L} = \mathcal{L}_1 \cup \dots \cup \mathcal{L}_k$. Since $|\mathcal{L}| = m > kn$, there is some \mathcal{L}_i with at least $n + 1$ elements. This is in contradiction with the assumption that any $n + 1$ elements in \mathcal{L} are linearly independent. \square

For the remaining of the section, we fix some $r \leq \ell$ and a covering collection \mathcal{L} for $(\mathbb{P}^{n-1})^{\ell-1}$ and choose, for each $L_i \in \mathcal{L}$, different linear forms $L'_1, \dots, L'_{n-1} \in \mathcal{L} \setminus \{L_i\}$.

Definition 4.8. We write $\widehat{L}_i : \{u \in \mathbb{P}^{n-1} \mid L_i(u) \neq 0\} \rightarrow \mathbb{C}^{n-1}$ for the map

$$\widehat{L}_i(u) = \left(\frac{L'_1(u)}{L_i(u)}, \dots, \frac{L'_{n-1}(u)}{L_i(u)} \right).$$

Recall how the coverings for the case of $X = \mathbb{C}^2$ were indexed: If we are only interested in double points, that is, if $\ell = 2$, then two open subsets indexed by $i = 1, 2$ are enough. If we are interested in triple points, that is, $\ell = 3$, then we covered the spaces B_2 and $(B_2/\mathbb{C}^2)^2$ by three open subsets indexed by $i = 1, 2, 3$. The space B_3 was then covered by six open subsets U_{ij} , with multi-indices (i, j) , with $i = 1, 2, 3$ and $j = 1, 2$.

In general, we shall define a set of multi-indices $\alpha = (\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_{r-1})$ for our open cover of $(B_r/B_{r-1})^s$ in such a way that, for every $i \leq r$, the family $\{L_{\alpha_i} \mid \alpha \in S_r\}$ is a covering collection for $(\mathbb{P}^{n-1})^{\ell-i-1}$.

Definition 4.9. For $r \geq 2$, we let S_r^ℓ be the set of multi-indices $\alpha = (\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_{r-1})$, where the α_i are integer numbers satisfying

$$\begin{aligned} 1 &\leq \alpha_1 \leq (\ell - 1)(n - 1) + 1, \\ 1 &\leq \alpha_2 \leq (\ell - 2)(n - 1) + 1, \\ &\vdots \\ 1 &\leq \alpha_{r-1} \leq (\ell - r - 1)(n - 1) + 1. \end{aligned}$$

If $r > 2$, we have a map $S_r^\ell \rightarrow S_{r-1}^\ell$ given by

$$(\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_{r-1}) \mapsto (\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_{r-2}).$$

We set $S_1^\ell = \{0\}$ and let $S_2^\ell \rightarrow S_1^\ell$ be the constant map.

From now on, we fix a positive integer s , satisfying $r + s \leq \ell + 1$.

Definition 4.10. For each $\alpha \in S_r$, we write U_α^s for the subset of $\mathbb{C}^n \times (\mathbb{P}^{n-1})^{(r-1)(s-1+r/2)}$, consisting of tuples of points

$$\begin{array}{cccc} u^{(r-1, r+s-2)} & \dots & u^{(r-1, r-1)} & \\ \vdots & & \vdots & \ddots \\ u^{(1, r+s-2)} & \dots & u^{(1, r-1)} & \dots & u^{(1, 1)} \\ x^{(r+s-2)} & \dots & x^{(r-1)} & \dots & x^{(1)} & x \end{array} \tag{P}$$

with $x, x^{(j)} \in \mathbb{C}^n$, $u^{(i, j)} \in \mathbb{P}^{n-1}$ and $L_{\alpha_i}(u^{(i, j)}) \neq 0$, subject to the following iteratively defined conditions: First, set

$$\gamma^{(0, 0)} = x, \gamma^{(0, 1)} = x^{(1)}, \dots, \gamma^{(0, r+s-2)} = x^{(r+s-2)}.$$

Then, for each $1 \leq i \leq r$, set $\delta^{(i, j)} = \gamma^{(i-1, j)} - \gamma^{(i-1, i-1)}$, impose the condition

$$u^{(i, j)} \wedge \delta^{(i, j)} = 0$$

and, for $j = i, \dots, r + s - 2$, set

$$\lambda^{(i,j)} = L_{\alpha_i}(\delta^{(i,j)}) \in \mathbb{C}, \quad a^{(i,j)} = \widehat{L}_{\alpha_i}(u^{(i,j)}) \in \mathbb{C}^{n-1}, \quad \gamma^{(i,j)} = (\lambda^{(i,j)}, a^{(i,j)}).$$

The unusual placement of coordinates in (P) is designed to match the diagram (T_B) in Remark 4.5. We refer to the columns of (P) decreasingly from $r + s - 2$ to 0, so that the j th column is the one containing $x^{(j)}$.

Proposition 4.11. *The space $(B_r/B_{r-1})^s$ is a glueing of the spaces U_α^s , with $\alpha \in S_r^\ell$. For each multi-index $\alpha \in S_r^\ell$, the map $(B_r/B_{r-1})^s \rightarrow (B_r/B_{r-1})^{s-1}$ restricts to the map*

$$U_\alpha^s \rightarrow U_\alpha^{s-1}$$

which drops the left column of (P) . For $r \geq 2$, the map $(B_r/B_{r-1})^s \rightarrow (B_{r-1}/B_{r-2})^{s+1}$ restricts to the map

$$U_\alpha^s \rightarrow U_{(\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_{r-2})}^s$$

which drops the top row of (P) (in the case of $r = 2$, the index $(\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_{r-2})$ is meant to be $0 \in S_1^\ell$).

Proof. We proceed by induction on r . Together with the statement, we will need to show the following extra items, for a point in U_α^s whose coordinates form the pyramid (P) :

- (1) For positive $j \geq r$, the pyramid (P) has the j th column equal to the $(r - 1)$ th column if and only if $\delta^{(r,j)} = 0$. In particular, the diagonal of $(B_r/B_{r-1})^2$ intersects U_α^2 at $\delta^{(r,r)} = 0$.
- (2) For positive $j \geq r$ and $j' \geq r$, the pyramid (P) has the j th column equal to the j' th column if and only if $\delta^{(r,j)} = \delta^{(r,j')}$.

The case of $r = 1$ is trivial: For each $s \geq 1$ we consider a single set $U_0^s = \mathbb{C}^n \times \dots \times \mathbb{C}^n$, with coordinates $x^{(s-1)}, \dots, x^{(1)}, x$. The map $(B_r/B_{r-1})^s \rightarrow (B_r/B_{r-1})^{s-1}$ drops $x^{(s-1)}$. The extra items (1) and (2) are obvious, since $\delta^{(1,j)} = x^{(j)} - x$ by definition.

Assume that the statement is true for $r - 1$. By item (1) of the induction hypothesis, on each U_α^2 , with $\alpha \in S_{r-1}^\ell$, the diagonal of $(B_{r-1}/B_{r-2})^2$ is regularly embedded by the equations $\delta^{(r-1,r-1)} = 0$. Consequently, over U_α^2 the space B_r is obtained by adding a new $u^{(r-1,r-1)}$ to the $x^{(j)}$ and $u^{(i,j)}$ of $(B_{r-1}/B_{r-2})^2$, and imposing the condition that $u^{(r-1,r-1)} \wedge \delta^{(r-1,r-1)} = 0$. The blowup $B_r \rightarrow (B_{r-1}/B_{r-2})^2$ drops $u^{(r-1,r-1)}$ and, by the induction hypothesis, $(B_{r-1}/B_{r-2})^2 \rightarrow B_{r-1}$ drops the remaining $u^{(i,r-1)}$ and $x^{(r-1)}$. Hence $B_r \rightarrow B_{r-1}$ drops the entire left column, and the fibered product $(B_r/B_{r-1})^s$ is obtained by adding new columns containing the $u^{(i,r+j-2)}$ and $x^{(r+j-2)}$, for $i = 1, \dots, r - 1$ and $j = 1, \dots, s$, each subject to its corresponding condition. The number of linear forms L_{α_i} that the multi-indices $\alpha \in S_r^\ell$ yield for each $1 \leq i \leq r - 1$ justifies, by Lemma 4.7, that the open subsets U_α^s cover $(B_r/B_{r-1})^s$. It is obvious that the map defined by dropping the top row satisfies the commutativities stated in Lemma 4.4 and therefore it is the desired map $(B_r/B_{r-1})^s \rightarrow (B_{r-1}/B_{r-2})^{s+1}$.

To show items (1) and (2), let $j \geq r$ and assume that a point satisfies

$$u^{(r-1,j)} = u^{(r-1,r-1)}, \dots, u^{(1,j)} = u^{(1,r-1)} \text{ and } x^{(j)} = x^{(r-1)}.$$

On U_{α}^S , the equality $u^{(r-1,j)} = u^{(r-1,r-1)}$ is equivalent to

$$\widehat{L}_{\alpha_{r-1}}(u^{(r-1,j)}) = \widehat{L}_{\alpha_{r-1}}(u^{(r-1,r-1)}),$$

that is, to $a^{(r-1,j)} = a^{(r-1,r-1)}$. By the induction hypothesis, applying item (2) on $U_{\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_{r-2}}^S$, it follows that the equations

$$u^{(r-2,j)} = u^{(r-2,r-1)}, \dots, u^{(1,j)} = u^{(1,r-1)}, x^{(j)} = x^{(r-1)}$$

are equivalent to $\delta^{(r-1,j)} = \delta^{(r-1,r-1)}$. Now observe that the conditions $u^{(r-1,j)} \wedge \delta^{(r-1,j)} = 0 = u^{(r-1,r-1)} \wedge \delta^{(r-1,j)}$ and $L_{\alpha_{r-1}}(u^{(r-1,j)}) \neq 0 \neq L_{\alpha_{r-1}}(u^{(r-1,r-1)})$ hold on U_{α} . Therefore, provided that $u^{(r-1,j)} = u^{(r-1,r-1)}$, the equality $\delta^{(r-1,j)} = \delta^{(r-1,r-1)}$ is equivalent to

$$L_{\alpha_{r-1}}(\delta^{(r-1,j)}) = L_{\alpha_{r-1}}(\delta^{(r-1,r-1)}),$$

that is, to $\lambda^{(r-1,j)} = \lambda^{(r-1,r-1)}$. Putting everything together, our initial conditions are equivalent to $\delta^{(r,j)} = 0$, and item (1) follows. To show item (2), assume

$$u^{(r-1,j)} = u^{(r-1,j')}, \dots, u^{(1,j)} = u^{(1,j')}, x^{(j)} = x^{(j')}.$$

On U_{α} , the condition $u^{(r-1,j)} = u^{(r-1,j')}$ is equivalent to $a^{(r-1,j)} = a^{(r-1,j')}$ and, by the induction hypothesis, the rest of conditions are equivalent to $\delta^{(r-1,j)} = \delta^{(r-1,j')}$. As before, provided that $u^{(r-1,j)} = u^{(r-1,j')}$ holds, the condition that $\delta^{(r-1,j)} = \delta^{(r-1,j')}$ is equivalent to $\lambda^{(r-1,j)} = \lambda^{(r-1,j')}$, because $u^{(r-1,j)} \wedge \delta^{(r-1,j)} = 0 = u^{(r-1,j')} \wedge \delta^{(r-1,j')}$. Therefore, our initial conditions are equivalent to $\delta^{(r,j)} = \delta^{(r,j')}$. This finishes the proof of item (2). \square

Definition 4.12. For each $L \in \mathcal{L}$, we write $\Lambda_L : \mathbb{C}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{C}^n$ for the linear isomorphism

$$x \mapsto (L(x), L'_1(x), \dots, L'_{n-1}(x)).$$

We write $\nu_L : \mathbb{C}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{C}^n$ for the map taking a point $\gamma = (\lambda, a)$, with $\lambda \in \mathbb{C}$ and $a = (a_1, \dots, a_{n-1}) \in \mathbb{C}^{n-1}$, to the point

$$\nu_L(\gamma) = \lambda \cdot \Lambda_L^{-1}(1, a_1, \dots, a_{n-1}).$$

To simplify notation, once a multi-index α is fixed, we write $\nu_i = \nu_{L_{\alpha_i}}$.

Reviewing the proof of Proposition 4.11, it becomes clear that, for each open subset U_{α}^S , the $x, \gamma^{(1,1)}, \gamma^{(2,2)}, \dots, \gamma^{(r-1,r-1)}, \gamma^{(r-1,r)}, \dots, \gamma^{(r-1,r+s-2)}$ are subject to no relations. For $(B_3/B_2)^2$, these are marked with the symbol ‘•’ in the diagram.

The remaining $\gamma^{(i,j)}$, marked with ‘o’, are determined by the ‘•’ entries, by means of the relations

$$\gamma^{(i,j)} = \gamma^{(i,i)} + \nu_{i+1}(\gamma^{(i+1,j)}),$$

corresponding to the arrows in the diagram. Then, from the pyramid

$$\begin{array}{ccccccc} \gamma^{(r-1,r+s-2)} & \dots & \gamma^{(r-1,r-1)} & & & & \\ \vdots & & \vdots & & \ddots & & \\ \gamma^{(1,r+s-2)} & \dots & \gamma^{(1,r-1)} & \dots & \gamma^{(1,1)} & & \\ \gamma^{(0,r+s-2)} & \dots & \gamma^{(0,r-1)} & \dots & \gamma^{(0,1)} & x & \end{array}$$

with $\gamma^{(i,j)} = (\lambda^{(i,j)}, a^{(i,j)})$, the $u^{(i,j)}$ and $x^{(j)}$ are recovered by setting

$$u^{(i,j)} = [\Lambda_{L_{\alpha_i}}^{-1}(1, a_1^{(i,j)}, \dots, a_{n-1}^{(i,j)})] \in \mathbb{P}^{n-1}, \quad x^{(j)} = x + \gamma^{(0,j)}.$$

This shows how to produce charts for the open subsets U_α :

Proposition 4.13. *Each $U_\alpha^s \subseteq (B_r/B_{r-1})^s$ is isomorphic to $(\mathbb{C}^n)^{r+s-1}$, via the map that takes a point $x, x^{(j)}, u^{(i,j)}$ to the point with coordinates $x, \gamma^{(1,1)}, \gamma^{(2,2)}, \dots, \gamma^{(r-1,r-1)}, \gamma^{(r-1,r)}, \dots, \gamma^{(r-1,r+s-2)}$.*

Since we are mainly interested in the spaces $B_r = (B_r/B_{r-1})^1$, we may take $\ell = r$. We write $S_r = S_r^\ell$ and $U_\alpha = U_\alpha^1$, as well as

$$\gamma^{(i)} = \gamma^{(i,i)}, \quad \lambda^{(i)} = \lambda^{(i,i)} \quad \text{and} \quad a^{(i)} = a^{(i,i)}.$$

This way B_r is covered by the open subsets U_α , with $\alpha \in S_r$, and we write $\varphi_\alpha : U_\alpha \rightarrow (\mathbb{C}^n)^r$ for the charts giving the coordinates

$$x, \gamma^{(1)}, \dots, \gamma^{(r-1)}.$$

5 | EQUATIONS FOR THE MULTIPLE POINT SPACES K_r

Here we give an explicit set of local equations for $K_r(f)$ in the coordinates of the affine open subsets described above.

Definition 5.1. With the previous notations, for any $\alpha \in S_r$ and any $f : \mathbb{C}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{C}^p$, we define the *iterated generalized divided differences* as follows: The first *generalized divided difference* is

$$f_{\alpha_1}[x, \gamma] = \frac{f(x + \nu_1(\gamma)) - f(x)}{\lambda}.$$

The j th iterated generalized divided difference is

$$\begin{aligned} & f_{\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_j}[x, \gamma^{(1)}, \dots, \gamma^{(j)}] \\ &= \frac{f_{\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_{j-1}}[x, \gamma^{(1)} \dots, \gamma^{(j-2)}, \gamma^{(j-1,j)}] - f_{\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_{j-1}}[x, \gamma^{(1)}, \dots, \gamma^{(j-1)}]}{\lambda^{(j)}}, \end{aligned}$$

where $\gamma^{(j-1,j)}$ stands for the function $\gamma^{(j-1)} + \nu_j(\gamma^{(j)})$. We omit the multi-indices α if there is no risk of confusion.

Theorem 5.2. *The space $K_r \cap U_\alpha$ is mapped isomorphically by φ_α to the zero locus of the ideal sheaf generated by*

$$f[x, \gamma^{(1)}], \dots, f[x, \gamma^{(1)}, \dots, \gamma^{(r-1)}].$$

Proof. We proceed by induction on r . By Theorem 3.1, we have:

$$\begin{aligned} K_r &= b^{-1}(K_{r-1} \times_{K_{r-2}} K_{r-1}) : b^{-1}(\Delta B_{r-1}) \\ &= b^{-1}(K_{r-1} \times_{K_{r-2}} K_{r-1}) : b^{-1}(\Delta K_{r-1}), \end{aligned}$$

since $(K_{r-1} \times_{K_{r-2}} K_{r-1}) \cap \Delta B_{r-1} = \Delta K_{r-1}$. Now observe that this quotient can be computed in $p^{-1}(K_{r-1})$ instead of B_r . Indeed, there are inclusions

$$\Delta K_{r-1} \subseteq K_{r-1} \times_{K_{r-2}} K_{r-1} \subseteq \pi_1^{-1}(K_{r-1}),$$

where $\pi_1 : B_{r-1} \times_{B_{r-2}} B_{r-1} \rightarrow B_{r-1}$ is the projection onto the first factor, and hence

$$b^{-1}(\Delta K_{r-1}) \subseteq b^{-1}(K_{r-1} \times_{K_{r-2}} K_{r-1}) \subseteq p^{-1}(K_{r-1}).$$

The induction hypothesis states that $p^{-1}(K_{r-1})$ is defined in the coordinate system $(U_\alpha, \varphi_\alpha)$ of B_r by the ideal sheaf I generated by the coordinate functions of

$$f[x, \gamma^{(1)}], \dots, f[x, \gamma^{(1)}, \dots, \gamma^{(r-2)}].$$

As subspaces of $p^{-1}(K_{r-1})$, the spaces $b^{-1}(\Delta K_{r-1})$ and $b^{-1}(K_{r-1} \times_{K_{r-2}} K_{r-1})$ are defined on $(U_\alpha, \varphi_\alpha)$ by the ideal sheaves generated by the class of $\lambda^{(r-1)}$ and the classes of the coordinate functions of

$$f[x, \gamma^{(1)}, \dots, \gamma^{(r-2)} + \nu_{r-1}(\gamma^{(r-1)})],$$

respectively. Observe that, modulo I , we have the equality

$$f[x, \gamma^{(1)}, \dots, \gamma^{(r-2)} + \nu_{r-1}(\gamma^{(r-1)})] = \lambda^{(r-1)} f[x, \gamma^{(1)}, \dots, \gamma^{(r-1)}].$$

Since $\lambda^{(r-1)}$ is not a zero divisor in \mathcal{O}_{U_α}/I , this implies that the defining ideal sheaf of K_r as a complex subspace of $p^{-1}(K_{r-1})$ is generated in $(U_\alpha, \varphi_\alpha)$ by the classes of the coordinate functions of $f[x, \gamma^{(1)}, \dots, \gamma^{(r-1)}]$. \square

Remark 5.3. It follows from Theorem 5.2 that, for a mapping f between complex manifolds, the local generators of the ideal sheaf defining $K^r(f)$ are obtained one by one from the coordinate functions of f . This implies that Proposition 2.14 holds for mappings between manifolds (the generalization to mappings between complex spaces is given next to Proposition 2.14).

Example 5.4. The double points K_2 of a map $f : \mathbb{C}^2 \rightarrow \mathbb{C}^p$ are given by the vanishing of the divided differences

$$f_1[(x, y), \gamma^{(1)}] = \frac{f(x + \lambda, y + \lambda a) - f(x, y)}{\lambda}, \text{ on the open subset } U_1,$$

$$f_2[(x, y), \gamma^{(1)}] = \frac{f(x + \lambda a, y + \lambda) - f(x, y)}{\lambda}, \text{ on the open subset } U_2.$$

If we wish to study triple points, then we need to add the open subset U_3 , where double points are given by the vanishing of

$$f_3[(x, y), \gamma^{(1)}] = \frac{f(x + \lambda, y + \lambda(a - 1)) - f(x, y)}{\lambda}.$$

The triple points of f on U_{11} are given by the vanishing of $f_1[(x, y), \gamma^{(1)}]$ and the second divided difference

$$f_{11}[(x, y), \gamma^{(1)}, \gamma^{(2)}] = \frac{f_1[(x, y), (\lambda + \mu, a + \mu b)] - f_1[(x, y), (\lambda, a)]}{\mu}$$

$$= \frac{\frac{f(x + \lambda + \mu, y + (\lambda + \mu)(a + \mu b)) - f(x, y)}{\lambda + \mu} - \frac{f(x + \lambda, y + \lambda a) - f(x, y)}{\lambda}}{\mu}.$$

On U_{12} , triple points are given by the vanishing of $f_1[(x, y), \gamma^{(1)}]$ and

$$f_{12}[(x, y), \gamma^{(1)}, \gamma^{(2)}] = \frac{f_1[(x, y), (\lambda + \mu b, a + \mu)] - f_1[(x, y), (\lambda, a)]}{\mu}$$

$$= \frac{\frac{f(x + \lambda + \mu b, y + (\lambda + \mu b)(a + \mu)) - f(x, y)}{\lambda + \mu b} - \frac{f(x + \lambda, y + \lambda a) - f(x, y)}{\lambda}}{\mu},$$

and similarly for the remaining open subsets U_{21}, U_{22}, U_{31} and U_{32} of the covering of B_3 . This formulas are used explicitly in Example 5.12.

Definition 5.5. We say that K_r is *dimensionally correct* if $\dim K_r = nr - p(r - 1)$.

Corollary 5.6. Let $X^n \rightarrow Y^p$ be a map between complex manifolds. The dimension of K_r is at least $nr - p(r - 1)$ at any point. If K_r is dimensionally correct, then it is locally a complete intersection in B_r .

Proof. This follows from the fact that K_r is locally defined by $p(r - 1)$ equations in B_r . □

We finish this section by explaining how the computations can be simplified for maps of lower corank, and giving an example. Recall that two maps $f : X \rightarrow Y$ and $f' : X' \rightarrow Y'$ between manifolds are called *\mathcal{A} -equivalent* if there exist two biholomorphisms $\phi : X \rightarrow X'$ and $\psi : Y \rightarrow Y'$, such that $f' = \psi \circ f' \circ \phi^{-1}$. As a consequence of Theorem 2.13, we obtain the following:

Proposition 5.7. If f and f' are \mathcal{A} -equivalent maps, then $K_r(f) \cong K_r(f')$ via an isomorphism $B_r(X) \cong B_r(X')$ induced by ϕ .

A map $F : T \times X \rightarrow T \times Y$ of the form $F(x, t) = (t, f_t(x))$ is said to be an *unfolding* of the map $f_{t_0} : X \rightarrow Y$, for each $t_0 \in T$. The manifold T is called the parameter space. Recall that, by Proposition 2.15, the multiple point space $K_r(F)$ is canonically embedded in $T \times B_r(\mathbb{C}^n)$, and $K_r(F) \cap \{t = t_0\} = K_r(f_{t_0})$. One checks easily that $K_r(F)$ is computed as follows:

Proposition 5.8. *Let $F : T \times \mathbb{C}^n \rightarrow T \times \mathbb{C}^p$ be an unfolding of the form $F(t, x) = (t, f_t(x))$ and fix a covering collection of $(\mathbb{P}^{n-1})^{r-1}$. In each of the open subsets $T \times U_\alpha$, $\alpha \in S_r$, the multiple point space $K_r(F)$ is given by the vanishing of*

$$f_t[x, \gamma^{(1)}], \dots, f_t[x, \gamma^{(1)}, \dots, \gamma^{(r-1)}].$$

Definition 5.9. In the setting above, we call $f_t[x, \gamma^{(1)}, \dots, \gamma^{(s)}]$ the *relative divided differences* of $f_t(x)$.

Remark 5.10. If f has corank k at x and $\dim X = n$, then locally f is \mathcal{A} -equivalent to an $(n - k)$ -parameter unfolding. In particular, the relative divided differences of double and triple points of maps of corank two maps are as in Example 5.4.

For a corank one map germ $f : (\mathbb{C}^n, 0) \rightarrow (\mathbb{C}^p, 0)$ we obtain the normal form

$$(x_1, \dots, x_{n-1}, y) \mapsto (x_1, \dots, x_{n-1}, f_n(x, y), \dots, f_p(x, y)).$$

The multiple points $K_r(f)$ of a map in such a form can be embedded in $\mathbb{C}^{n-1} \times B_r(\mathbb{C}) = \mathbb{C}^{n-1} \times \mathbb{C}^r$. In this case, our atlas consists on a single chart, and the relative divided differences are the following expressions:

$$\begin{aligned} f[x, y, y^{(1)}] &= \frac{f(x, y^{(1)}) - f(x, y)}{y^{(1)} - y}, \\ f[x, y, y^{(1)}, y^{(2)}] &= \frac{f[x, y, y^{(2)}] - f[x, y, y^{(1)}]}{y^{(2)} - y^{(1)}}, \\ &\vdots \\ f[x, y, \dots, y^{(r-1)}] &= \frac{f[x, y, y^{(1)}, \dots, y^{(r-3)}, y^{(r-1)}] - f[x, y, y^{(1)}, \dots, y^{(r-2)}]}{y^{(r-1)} - y^{(r-2)}}. \end{aligned}$$

These expressions were introduced by Marar and Mond’s in [16] as equations for their multiple point space $D^r(f)$ of a corank one map. Consequently, we obtain the following result.

Corollary 5.11. *If f is a corank one map, then $K_r(f)$ and $D^r(f)$ are equal.*

For arbitrary corank, a space $D^2(f) \subseteq X \times X$ was introduced by Mond in [20]. A general construction of multiple point spaces $D^r(f) \subseteq X^r$ was given by the authors in [25] (see also [22, Section 9.2]).

Example 5.12. We are going to compute the spaces K_2 and K_3 of the map $f : \mathbb{C}^3 \rightarrow \mathbb{C}^4$ given by

$$(t, x, y) \mapsto (t, x^2 + ty, y^2 - tx, x^3 + y^3 + xy).$$

FIGURE 1 Maps unfolded by f

One checks easily that f has an isolated point of corank 2 at the origin. Furthermore, f and is a one-parameter unfolding and, for $\epsilon \neq 0$, the mapping $f(\epsilon, x, y)$ has three crosscaps and a triple point, collapsing to the origin as ϵ tends to zero. One may think of the mappings $f(0, x, y)$ and $f(\epsilon, x, y)$ as complex versions of the mappings depicted in Figure 1.

Since f is an unfolding, Proposition 5.8 ensures that we may compute K_r as a subspace of $\mathbb{C} \times B_r(\mathbb{C}^2)$ by means of the relative divided differences. As already mentioned, the expressions from Example 5.4 compute double and triple points of maps of corank two, leaving t as a parameter. In what follows, the notation for the atlas and divided differences is taken from there.

In the chart $\varphi_1 : U_1 \rightarrow \mathbb{C}^5$, with coordinates (t, x, y, λ, a) , the equations for $K_2 \cap U_1$ are the vanishing of the divided differences of f_2, f_3 and f_4 :

$$0 = at + \lambda + 2x,$$

$$0 = a^2\lambda + 2ay - t,$$

$$0 = a^3\lambda^2 + 3a^2\lambda y + a\lambda + ax + 3ay^2 + \lambda^2 + 3\lambda x + 3x^2 + y.$$

These computations can be performed with the library `IteratedMultPoint.lib` for SINGULAR, by means of the sequence of commands

- LIB "IteratedMultPoint.lib";
- ring r=0, (t,x,y), dp;
- list f=t,x2+ty,y2-tx,x3+y3+xy;
- ring S2=ItMP(f,2);
- L[1];

The instruction `ItMP(f,2)` returns a ring with variables $t, x, y, l(1), a(1)$, containing a list L . The first entry $L[1]$ has the equations of K_2 on the open subset U_1 . The variables $l(1), a(1)$ correspond to λ and a . The space $K_2 \cap U_1$ has dimension 2 and thus M_2 is dimensionally correct and a complete intersection on U_1 . The projection $K_2 \cap U_1 \rightarrow \mathbb{C} \times (\mathbb{C}^2)^2$, with coordinates $(t, (x, y), (x', y'))$, is described by

$$x' = x + \lambda, \quad y' = y + \lambda a.$$

In order to cover K_2 , the divided differences on U_2 must be computed. We omit them, as they yield nothing new. The equations for $K_2 \cap U_2$ on SINGULAR are the content of the entry $L[2]$.

Now we move to the computation of triple points K_3 . As part of the process for triple points, we must compute double points in the extra open subset U_3 . Again, this computation is uninteresting and omitted.

We proceed now to the computation of the triple point space K_3 on the chart $\varphi_{11} : U_{11} \rightarrow \mathbb{C}^7$ of $\mathbb{C} \times B_3(\mathbb{C}^2)$, with coordinates $(t, x, y, \lambda, a, \mu, b)$. To the three equations for K_2 on U_1 found above, the vanishing of the following second divided differences must be added:

$$0 = bt + 1,$$

$$0 = a^2 + 2ab\lambda + 2ab\mu + b^2\lambda\mu + b^2\mu^2 + 2by,$$

$$\begin{aligned} 0 = & 2a^3\lambda + a^3\mu + 3a^2b\lambda^2 + 6a^2b\lambda\mu + 3a^2b\mu^2 + 3a^2y + 3ab^2\lambda^2\mu \\ & + 6ab^2\lambda\mu^2 + 3ab^2\mu^3 + 6ab\lambda y + 6ab\mu y + a + b^3\lambda^2\mu^2 + 2b^3\lambda\mu^3 \\ & + b^3\mu^4 + 3b^2\lambda\mu y + 3b^2\mu^2y + b\lambda + b\mu + bx + 3by^2 + 2\lambda + \mu + 3. \end{aligned}$$

These triple points are computed on SINGULAR by means of the sequence

- LIB "IteratedMultPoint.lib";
- ring r=0, (t,x,y), dp;
- list f=t,x2+ty,y2-tx,x3+y3+xy;
- ring S3=ItMP(f,3);
- L[1][1];

This time ItMP(f,3) returns a ring with variables $t, x, y, l(1), l(2), a(1), a(2)$, together with a list whose entries $L[i][j]$ contain equations for the spaces $K_3 \cap U_{ij}$, for $1 \leq i \leq 3$ and $1 \leq j \leq 2$.

SINGULAR can also be used to check that $K_3 \cap U_{11}$ has dimension 1, and hence it is dimensionally correct and a complete intersection. Explicit equations for the projection of $K_3 \cap U_{11}$ on $\mathbb{C} \times (\mathbb{C}^2)^3$ are obtained by putting

$$x' = x + \lambda, \quad y' = y + \lambda a, \quad x'' = x + \lambda + \mu, \quad y'' = y + (\lambda + \mu)(a + \mu b).$$

The situation changes when we compute K_3 on U_{12} . On this open subset, the first divided differences are the same, but the iterated ones are

$$0 = 2x + \lambda\mu + \mu^2b + 2\lambda a + 2\mu ab + a^2b,$$

$$0 = -t + b,$$

$$\begin{aligned} 0 = & 3x^2 + 3x\lambda\mu + 3x\mu^2b + 6x\lambda a + 6x\mu ab + 3xa^2b + 3yb + y \\ & + \lambda^2\mu^2 + 2\lambda\mu^3b + \mu^4b^2 + 3\lambda^2\lambda a + 6\lambda\mu^2ab + 3\mu^3ab^2 + 3\lambda^2a^2 \\ & + 6\lambda\mu a^2b + 3\mu^2a^2b^2 + 2\lambda a^3b + 2\lambda b + \lambda + \mu a^3b^2 + \mu b^2 + \mu b + ab. \end{aligned}$$

The equations of K_3 on U_{12} are contained in $L[1][2]$ and a computation with SINGULAR shows that $K_3 \cap U_{12}$ has dimension two. As a consequence, K_3 is not dimensionally correct. The image of the projection $K_3 \cap U_{12} \rightarrow \mathbb{C} \times (\mathbb{C}^2)^3$ is obtained by putting

$$x' = x + \lambda, \quad y' = y + \lambda a, \quad x'' = x + \lambda + \mu b, \quad y'' = y + (\lambda + \mu b)(a + \mu).$$

Somehow surprisingly, the images of $K_3 \cap U_{11}$ and $K_3 \cap U_{12}$ on $\mathbb{C} \times (\mathbb{C}^2)^3$ are the same, despite coming from spaces of different dimensions (again, this can be checked with SINGULAR). A moment of thought will convince the reader of the fact that this implies that K_3 has an irreducible component contained in the exceptional divisor of $B_3 \rightarrow B_2 \times_{\mathbb{C}^3} B_2$. This and other related pathologies are explained in the next section.

Remark 5.13. When using the library `IteratedMultiPoint.lib` on an s -parameter unfolding f , it is convenient to introduce the s parameters in the front of the list of polynomials defining f . This way, the procedure `ItMP(f,r)`; makes computations in $\mathbb{C}^s \times B_r(\mathbb{C}^{n-s})$, as indicated in Proposition 5.8. If, for example, we were to reorder the coordinate functions of the previous example as `list f=x2+ty,y2-tx,x3+y3+xy,t`, the equations will be given in $B_r(\mathbb{C}^3)$. The equations and the coverings would still be correct, but more complicated.

Remark 5.14. The computation of `ItMP(f,r)` involves choosing a covering collection for $(\mathbb{P}^{n-1})^{r-1}$, which the procedure does internally. A different collection will give the same space K_r , but may result in very different covering and equations.

6 | PATHOLOGIES

As Kleiman observes in [11], the idea that K_r is the double point space of $K_{r-1} \rightarrow K_{r-2}$ is just a definition, with a clear interpretation only for strict multiple points. As it turns out, in the presence of points of corank ≥ 2 the iteration principle may yield too many points, and may do so in a non-symmetrical way. These pathologies come as no surprise; the excess of dimension and the fact that K_r and the target multiple points disagree are somehow easy set-theoretical considerations, while the lack of symmetry was already pointed out by Ran in [31, Section 1]. Our explicit description of K_r just allows us to be more precise about them, something that will be crucial for results in the sequel of this work [26].

6.1 | Excess of dimension

Assume that a map $f : X \rightarrow Y$ between manifolds has corank ≥ 2 at $x \in X$. Following the description of double points in Proposition 2.11, we may take any two different points $u^{(1)}, u^{(2)} \in \mathbb{P}(\ker df_x)$ to produce two double points $(x, x, u^{(1)})$ and $(x, x, u^{(2)})$. Since the map $B_2 \rightarrow X$ drops the $u^{(i)}$, these two points form a point in $K_2 \times_{K_1} K_2$ away from ΔB_2 . This point is the image of a point in B_3 under the map $B_3 \rightarrow B_2 \times_{B_1} B_2$, which locally is an isomorphism. Since this preimage is not contained in the exceptional divisor, it is contained in $K_3 = b^{-1}(K_2 \times_{K_1} K_2) : b^{-1}(\Delta B_2)$.

Summarizing, any pair of different points $u, u' \in \mathbb{P}(\ker df_x)$ produces a triple point, with no further conditions on u, u' . The argument carries on to higher multiple spaces; the following result counts exactly how many points are obtained this way.

Proposition 6.1. *Let f be a map between manifolds, let x be a point where the corank of f is $k \geq 2$ and let $r \geq 2$. The preimage of $(x, \dots, x) \in X^r$ by the map $K_r \rightarrow X^r$ has dimension $(r-1)(k-1)$.*

Proof. First we show that the dimension is at least $(r - 1)(k - 1)$, by showing that any tuple $(u^{(1)}, \dots, u^{(r-1)})$ of different points $u^{(i)} \in \mathbb{P}(\ker df_x)$ can be identified with a point in K_r mapping to (x, \dots, x) . The case of $r \geq 2$ was shown above. The case of $r \geq 3$ is analogous since, as one can check easily, a tuple $(u^{(1)}, \dots, u^{(r-1)})$ with all $u^{(i)}$ different determines a unique point in B_r , and the map $B_r \rightarrow B_{r-1}$ just drops the last component $u^{(r-1)}$.

Now we show that the dimension is at most $(r - 1)(k - 1)$. As a consequence of Proposition 4.2, it suffices to show the claim for a map germ $f : (\mathbb{C}^n, 0) \rightarrow (\mathbb{C}^p, 0)$ of corank k , which by Proposition 2.5 may be taken of the form

$$f(x) = (x_1, \dots, x_{n-k}, h(x)).$$

Following Proposition 2.15, the space K_r can be embedded in $\mathbb{C}^{n-k} \times B_r(\mathbb{C}^k)$. Under this embedding, the points mapping to (x, \dots, x) we are looking for now correspond to points mapping to

$$(x_1, \dots, x_{n-k}, (y, \dots, y)),$$

where $y = x_{n-k+1}, \dots, x_n$. Therefore, the dimension we want to compute is at most the dimension of the preimage of (y, \dots, y) by the map $B_r(\mathbb{C}^k) \rightarrow (\mathbb{C}^k)^r$. In any of the charts from Section 4, this set is given by $\lambda^{(i)} = 0$. The free $a^{(i)}$, with $i = 1, \dots, r - 1$, give a fiber of dimension $(r - 1)(k - 1)$. \square

Corollary 6.2. *Let $f : X \rightarrow Y$ between complex manifolds, with points of corank $k \geq 2$, and assume that $\dim X - \dim Y \leq k$. Then there exists r_0 such that K_r is not dimensionally correct, for all $r \geq r_0$.*

6.2 | K_r and target multiple points

Kleiman, Lipman and Ulrich [14] studied relations between the multiple point spaces given by iteration and by the Fitting ideals. For any finite map $f : X \rightarrow Y$, the subspace $N_r(f) \subseteq Y$ is given by the vanishing of the $(r - 1)$ st Fitting ideal of $f_*\mathcal{O}_X$. The image of f is $N_1(f)$, the double points of f in Y are $N_2(f)$, and so on. Pulling back these points, we obtain the multiple point spaces $M_r(f) = f^{-1}(N_r(f)) \subseteq X$. Here, X and Y are not assumed to be smooth, and a suitable extended definition of corank is used. Write

$$K_{r+1} \xrightarrow{f_r} K_r$$

for the usual maps, and

$$K_r \xrightarrow{\rho_r} X$$

the maps obtained by composition.

For finite maps $f : X \rightarrow Y$ of corank one, with $\dim Y = \dim X + 1$, they show that

$$N_{r-1}(f_1) = M_r(f)$$

and that all f_r are finite maps of corank one. In this case, the maps ρ_r are also finite and have corank one, and one obtains the set-theoretical equality

$$N_1(\rho_r) = M_r(f).$$

This means that the projection $\rho_r(K_r)$ of the iterated multiple points K_r is the same as the inverse image $f^{-1}(N_r(f))$ of the target multiple points.

The first problem that one encounters in the case of $\text{corank} \geq 2$ is that the maps f_r , and hence the ρ_r are not finite anymore. Therefore their pushforward modules are not finitely presented modules, their Fitting ideals are not defined and it is not clear how one should define the algebraic structure of the projections $\rho_r(K_r)$. But the problem is worse, as $\rho_r(K_r)$ and $f^{-1}(N_r(f))$ do not agree even at the set-theoretical level. To see this, just observe that $N_r(f)$ is empty, for every r bigger than the multiplicity of f , while K_r is never empty in the presence of points of $\text{corank} \geq 2$, as a consequence of Proposition 6.1. It is worth mentioning that the spaces $N_r(f)$ have their own disadvantages compared to $K_r(f)$. The first is that they are only defined for finite mappings. The second is that they are hard to compute, since the calculation of Fitting ideals requires computing a presentation matrix of the pushforward module $f_*\mathcal{O}_X$, which is a very hard task when the corank of f is high. In contrast, and despite their pathologies, the spaces K_r have advantage of being given by the explicit equations of Theorem 5.2.

6.3 | Lack of symmetry

It is well known that the multiple point spaces $D^r \subseteq X^r$ are invariant by the action of the symmetric group S_r by permutation of the coordinates in X^r . It would be reasonable to expect the spaces B_r to have natural actions, lifting those on X^r , and that these actions restrict to actions on K_r compatible with those on D^r . We show that, unfortunately, this is not the case for $r \geq 3$. Before this, we show that, for a manifold X , the action of S_2 on X^2 can be lifted to B^2 , and indeed there is a unique way of doing it.

Let X be a complex manifold and $\sigma : X^2 \rightarrow X^2$ be the map corresponding to the transposition (1 2). To lift the action of S_2 on B_2 , we must find an involution $\tilde{\sigma} : B_2 \rightarrow B_2$, making the diagram

$$\begin{array}{ccc} B_2 & \xrightarrow{\tilde{\sigma}} & B_2 \\ \downarrow & & \downarrow \\ X^2 & \xrightarrow{\sigma} & X^2 \end{array}$$

commutative. For this we use the fact that B_2 is the blowup of X^2 along ΔX . Let h be the composite map $B_2 \rightarrow X^2 \xrightarrow{\sigma} X^2$. Since the preimage of ΔX by σ is again ΔX , the preimage $h^{-1}(\Delta X)$ is the exceptional divisor E of B_2 . The universal property of the blowup $B_2 \rightarrow X^2$ applies to h and gives a unique map $\tilde{\sigma}$ satisfying the above commutativity. The fact that $\tilde{\sigma}$ is an involution follows from the fact that $\tilde{\sigma}$ can be identified with σ on $B_2 \setminus E$, a dense subset of B_2 . We observe that the lift $\tilde{\sigma}$ is defined in local coordinates in the obvious way $\tilde{\sigma}(x_1, x_2, u) = (x_2, x_1, u)$.

Now we show that, for a complex manifold X of dimension at least 2, there is no action of S_3 on B^3 lifting the action on X^3 . We assume for simplicity that $X = \mathbb{C}^n$. Since the transposition (1 2) takes the set $\Delta_{13} = \{(x, x', x) \in X^3\}$ to $\Delta_{23} = \{(x', x, x) \in X^3\}$, it suffices to show that the preimages in B_3 of Δ_{13} and Δ_{23} are not isomorphic. We start by looking at the preimages of Δ_{13} and Δ_{23} in the space $B_2 \times_X B_2$. The space $B_2 \times_X B_2$ consists of points

$$\begin{array}{ccc} u' & u & \\ x'' & x' & x \end{array}$$

with $(x'' - x) \wedge u' = 0 = (x' - x) \wedge u$. At an open subset given by, say, $u'_i \neq 0 \neq u''_i$, the preimage of Δ_{12} is given by the equation $x'_i - x_i = 0$ and hence is a Cartier divisor. However, the preimage of Δ_{23} equals $Z \cup \Delta B_2$, where the diagonal B_2 is given by $x''_i = x'_i$ and $u' = u$, and Z is a codimension 2 component given by $x'_i = x''_i = 0$, which is not contained in ΔB_2 because $n \geq 2$.

On one hand, it is clear that the preimage of Δ_{13} is a divisor in B_3 , because it is the preimage of the corresponding preimage in $B_2 \times_X B_2$, which is already a divisor. On the other hand, the space B_3 is obtained by blowing up ΔB_2 , and therefore the preimage of ΔB_2 is also a divisor in B_3 . However, since the structure map of the blowup is an isomorphism away from the exceptional divisor, and Z is not contained in ΔB_2 , we conclude that the preimage of Δ_{13} has a component of codimension 2 arising from Z . This shows that the preimages of Δ_{13} and Δ_{23} are not isomorphic.

APPENDIX: SOME PROOFS

Two basic lemmas will be used, which follow immediately from the definition of the symmetric algebra.

Lemma A.1. *Any morphism $M \rightarrow N$ of R -modules extends uniquely to a morphism of R -algebras $S(M) \rightarrow S(N)$. Moreover, If $M \rightarrow N$ is an epimorphism (resp. isomorphism), then $S(M) \rightarrow S(N)$ is an epimorphism (resp. isomorphism).*

Lemma A.2. *For any ring morphism $R' \rightarrow R$ and any R -module M , there is unique graded morphism of algebras $S_{R'}(M) \rightarrow S_R(M)$, which is $R' \rightarrow R$ in degree zero and id_M in degree one. For all $d \geq 1$, the degree d part $(S_{R'}(M))_d \rightarrow (S_R(M))_d$ is an epimorphism, and it is an isomorphism if $R' \rightarrow R$ is an epimorphism.*

Proof 1 (Proposition 1.2). Given $e : X \hookrightarrow \mathcal{X}$, let $W = e^{-1}(\mathcal{W})$. We have an epimorphism of $\mathcal{O}_{\mathcal{X}}$ -modules

$$\mathcal{O}_{\mathcal{X}} \xrightarrow{e^\#} e_* \mathcal{O}_X,$$

which restricts to an epimorphism $I_{\mathcal{W}} \rightarrow e_* I_W$, where $I_{\mathcal{W}}$ and I_W are the ideals which define \mathcal{W} in \mathcal{X} and W in X , respectively. By Lemma A.1, this morphism extends to an epimorphism

$$S_{\mathcal{O}_{\mathcal{X}}}(I_{\mathcal{W}}) \rightarrow S_{\mathcal{O}_{\mathcal{X}}}(e_* I_W).$$

By Lemma A.2, there is also an epimorphism $S_{\mathcal{O}_{\mathcal{X}}}(e_* I_W) \rightarrow e_* S_{\mathcal{O}_X} I_W$. Composing these two epimorphisms we obtain $S_{\mathcal{O}_{\mathcal{X}}}(I_{\mathcal{W}}) \rightarrow e_* S_{\mathcal{O}_X}(I_W)$, which induces the monomorphism $\text{Res}_{\mathcal{W}} X \hookrightarrow \text{Res}_{\mathcal{W}} \mathcal{X}$. Functoriality follows from functoriality of the elements involved.

Proof 2 (Proposition 1.3). Assume that $X_i = V(J_i)$ and $\mathcal{W} = V(I)$ for some coherent ideal sheaves J_1, J_2 and I on X such that $J_2 \subseteq I$. We use the local description given after Definition 1.1 to show the required equality between the residual spaces. Let $r : \text{Res}_{\mathcal{W}} \mathcal{X} \rightarrow \mathcal{X}$ be the structure map. We take a point $x \in X$ and a small enough open neighborhood U of x in X .

Put $R = \mathcal{O}_{\mathcal{X}}(U)$ for simplicity. Given any $p \times q$ -matrix $M = (m_{ij})$ with entries in R we denote by \hat{M} the ideal in the polynomial ring $R[u_1, \dots, u_p]$ generated by the linear forms $\hat{M}_i = \sum m_{ij} u_j$, with $j = 1, \dots, q$.

We start with a presentation

$$R^q \xrightarrow{A} R^p \longrightarrow I(U) \longrightarrow 0,$$

Then $r^{-1}(U)$ is isomorphic to the complex subspace of $U \times \mathbb{P}^{p-1}$ given by the vanishing of \hat{A} . This will be our ambient space.

Assume that $I(U)$ is generated by $g_1, \dots, g_p \in R$ and $J_2(U)$ is generated by $h_1, \dots, h_s \in R$. Since $J_2(U) \subseteq I(U)$ we have $h_k = \sum b_{kj}g_j$ for some $p \times s$ -matrix $B = (b_{kj})$ also with entries in R . This gives a presentation of $I(U)/J_2(U)$ over R :

$$R^q \oplus R^s \xrightarrow{A+B} R^p \longrightarrow \frac{I(U)}{J_2(U)} \longrightarrow 0,$$

and tensoring with $S_2 = R/J_2(U)$,

$$S_2^q \oplus S_2^s \xrightarrow{\bar{A}+\bar{B}} S_2^p \longrightarrow \frac{I(U)}{J_2(U)} \longrightarrow 0.$$

Hence, $(\text{Res}_W X_2) \cap r^{-1}(U)$ is the complex subspace of $U \times \mathbb{P}^{p-1}$ given by the ideal $\hat{A} + \hat{B} + J_2(U)R[u_1, \dots, u_p]$.

Let $S_1 = R/J_1(U)$ and consider the ideal $(I(U) + J_1(U))/J_1(U)$ which defines $W \cap U$ in $X_1 \cap U$. Suppose we have a presentation:

$$S_1^t \xrightarrow{\bar{A}_1} S_1^p \longrightarrow \frac{I(U) + J_1(U)}{J_1(U)} \longrightarrow 0.$$

for some matrix $\bar{A}_1 = (\bar{a}_{ij})$ with entries in S_1 . We denote by $A_1 = (a_{ij})$ the matrix whose entries are now in R . We see $(\text{Res}_W X_1) \cap r^{-1}(U)$ as the subspace of $U \times \mathbb{P}^{p-1}$ defined by $\hat{A}_1 + J_1(U)R[u_1, \dots, u_p]$. Since $(\text{Res}_W X_1) \cap r^{-1}(U)$ is a subspace of $r^{-1}(U)$ we have

$$\hat{A} \subseteq \hat{A}_1 + J_1(U)R[u_1, \dots, u_p].$$

Finally, we compute $(\text{Res}_W X) \cap r^{-1}(U)$, where $X = X_1 \cap X_2$. We proceed as before:

$$S_1^t \oplus S_1^s \xrightarrow{\bar{A}_1+\bar{B}} S_1^p \longrightarrow \frac{I(U) + J_1(U)}{J_1(U) + J_2(U)} \longrightarrow 0,$$

and tensoring with $S = R/(J_1(U) + J_2(U))$,

$$S^t \oplus S^s \xrightarrow{\bar{A}_1+\bar{B}} S^p \longrightarrow \frac{I(U) + J_1(U)}{J_1(U) + J_2(U)} \longrightarrow 0.$$

Hence, $(\text{Res}_W X) \cap r^{-1}(U)$ is defined in $U \times \mathbb{P}^{p-1}$ by the ideal

$$\hat{A}_1 + \hat{B} + (J_1(U) + J_2(U))R[u_1, \dots, u_p].$$

It follows that

$$\begin{aligned} & (\hat{A}_1 + J_1(U)R[u_1, \dots, u_p]) + (\hat{A} + \hat{B} + J_2(U)R[u_1, \dots, u_p]) \\ &= \hat{A}_1 + \hat{B} + (J_1(U) + J_2(U))R[u_1, \dots, u_p], \end{aligned}$$

which implies

$$(\text{Res}_W X_1 \cap \text{Res}_W X_2) \cap r^{-1}(U) = (\text{Res}_W X) \cap r^{-1}(U).$$

Proof 3 (Lemma 1.6). Applying Remark 1.5 to the inclusions $\mathcal{W} \cap X \subset X \subset \mathcal{X}$, we obtain

$$\text{Res}_{\mathcal{W} \cap X} X = b^{-1}(X) : b^{-1}(\mathcal{W} \cap X).$$

We show that this space is isomorphic to $b_{\mathcal{W}}^{-1}(X) : b_{\mathcal{W}}^{-1}(\mathcal{W})$.

Let $\mathcal{W} = V(I)$ and $X = V(J)$, for some coherent ideal sheaves in \mathcal{X} . Assume that I is generated on an affine open subset $U \subseteq \mathcal{X}$ by a regular sequence $g_1, \dots, g_k \in \mathcal{O}_{\mathcal{X}}(U)$, which may be completed to a regular sequence $g_1, \dots, g_k, h_1, \dots, h_r$ generating $I + J$. We may also complete h_1, \dots, h_r with some p_1, \dots, p_l to get a set of generators of J .

The blowup $\text{Bl}_{\mathcal{W}} \mathcal{X}$ in $U' := b_{\mathcal{W}}^{-1}(U)$ is isomorphic to the complex subspace of $U \times \mathbb{P}^{k-1}$, defined by the vanishing of the 2×2 -minors of the matrix

$$\begin{pmatrix} g_1 & \cdots & g_k \\ u_1 & \cdots & u_k \end{pmatrix}$$

and $b_{\mathcal{W}}^{-1}(X)$ is obtained in U' just by adding the equations $h_1 = \dots = h_k = 0$ and $p_1 = \dots = p_l = 0$. For each $i = 1, \dots, k$, let U'_i be the affine open subset of $U \times \mathbb{P}^{k-1}$ given by $u_i = 1$. The space $b_{\mathcal{W}}^{-1}(X)$ is defined on U'_i by the ideal $A' = A'_1 + A'_2$, where:

- (1) A'_1 is generated by $g_s - g_i u_s$, with $s = 1, \dots, k, s \neq i$;
- (2) A'_2 is generated by h_1, \dots, h_r and p_1, \dots, p_l .

The preimage $b_{\mathcal{W}}^{-1}(\mathcal{W})$ is defined on U'_i by the ideal $B' = A'_1 + (g_i)$. Therefore

$$\begin{aligned} A' : B' &= (A'_1 + A'_2) : (A'_1 + (g_i)) \\ &= ((A'_1 + A'_2) : A'_1) \cap ((A'_1 + A'_2) : g_i) \\ &= (A'_1 + A'_2) : g_i. \end{aligned}$$

Analogously, $\text{Bl}_{\mathcal{W} \cap X} \mathcal{X}$ is defined on the open set $U'' := b^{-1}(U)$ as the closed complex subspace of $U \times \mathbb{P}^{k+r-1}$ given by the 2×2 -minors of the matrix

$$\begin{pmatrix} g_1 & \cdots & g_k & h_1 & \cdots & h_r \\ u_1 & \cdots & u_k & v_1 & \cdots & v_r \end{pmatrix}.$$

Here we cover $U \times \mathbb{P}^{k+r-1}$ by affine open subsets $U''_i = \{u_i = 1\}$, with $i = 1, \dots, k$, and $V''_j = \{v_j = 1\}$, with $j = 1, \dots, r$. On one hand, the defining ideal of $b^{-1}(X)$ in U''_i is $A'' = A''_1 + A''_2 + g_i V$, where:

- (1) A''_1 is generated by $g_s - g_i u_s$, with $s = 1, \dots, k, s \neq i$;
- (2) A''_2 is generated by h_1, \dots, h_r and p_1, \dots, p_l ;
- (3) V is generated by v_1, \dots, v_r .

The defining ideal of $b^{-1}(\mathcal{W} \cap X)$ in U''_i is $B'' = A''_1 + A''_2 + (g_i)$, hence:

$$\begin{aligned} A'' : B'' &= (A''_1 + A''_2 + g_i V) : (A''_1 + A''_2 + (g_i)) \\ &= (A''_1 + A''_2 + g_i V) : g_i \\ &= ((A''_1 + A''_2) : g_i) + V. \end{aligned}$$

We have an isomorphism

$$\frac{\mathcal{O}_{U''_i}}{A'' : B''} = \frac{\mathcal{O}_{U''_i}}{(A''_1 + A''_2) : g_i + V} \cong \frac{\mathcal{O}_{U'_i}}{(A'_1 + A'_2) : g_i} = \frac{\mathcal{O}_{U'_i}}{A' : B'},$$

induced by the map

$$\varphi : (b^{-1}(X) : b^{-1}(\mathcal{W})) \cap U'_i \rightarrow (b^{-1}(X) : b^{-1}(\mathcal{W} \cap X)) \cap U''_i,$$

given by $(x, [u]) \mapsto (x, [u, 0])$ for $x \in U$ and $u \in \mathbb{P}^{k-1}$. It follows that this map is an isomorphism of complex spaces.

On the other hand, the defining ideal of $b^{-1}(X)$ in V''_j is generated by g_1, \dots, g_k and h_1, \dots, h_r , which coincides with the defining ideal of $b^{-1}(\mathcal{W} \cap X)$. It follows that

$$(b^{-1}(X) : b^{-1}(\mathcal{W} \cap X)) \cap V''_j = \emptyset.$$

Therefore, the above isomorphisms from $(b^{-1}(X) : b^{-1}(\mathcal{W})) \cap U'_i$ to $(b^{-1}(X) : b^{-1}(\mathcal{W} \cap X)) \cap U''_i$ glue together to give an isomorphism of complex spaces

$$\varphi : (b^{-1}(X) : b^{-1}(\mathcal{W})) \rightarrow (b^{-1}(X) : b^{-1}(\mathcal{W} \cap X)).$$

Proof 4 (Proposition 4.2). To use induction on r we prove a slightly more detailed result. We write K_{r_i} for $K_{r_i}(f^{(i)})$, as the $f^{(i)}$ are clear from the context. Let $z \in K_r$ project to a point $w \in K_{r-1}$, via the map $K_r \rightarrow K_{r-1}$. We claim that $K_{r-1}(f)$, around w , is locally isomorphic to

$$K_{r_1} \times_Y \cdots \times_Y K_{r_s},$$

for a partition $r_1, \dots, r_s = r - 1$. But we also claim that one of the following statements holds:

- (1) K_r is locally isomorphic to

$$K_{r_1} \times_Y \cdots \times_Y K_{r_s} \times_Y K_1,$$

and the map $K_r \rightarrow K_{r-1}$ drops the last component.

- (2) K_r is locally isomorphic to

$$K_{r_1} \times_Y \cdots \times_Y K_{r_i+1} \times_Y \cdots \times_Y K_{r_s},$$

the map $K_r \rightarrow K_{r-1}$ being the restriction of

$$\text{id}_{K_{r_1}} \times \cdots \times (K_{r_i+1} \rightarrow K_{r_i}) \times \cdots \times \text{id}_{K_{r_s}}.$$

There is nothing to prove for K_1 and for K_2 there are two cases: if $z \in K_2$ is not contained in the exceptional divisor of B_2 , then locally K_2 is isomorphic to $X \times_Y X$, that is, $K_2 \cong K_1 \times_Y K_1$, which is case (1). On the exceptional divisor we are looking at $K_2 \rightarrow K_1$, which is case (2).

Now assume that the statement holds up to $r \geq 2$ and compute $K_r \times_{K_{r-1}} K_r$, around a point whose first projection is $z \in K_r$ and its second projection is $z' \in K_r$. Consider the following cases:

If K_r is of the form (1) around both z and z' , then $K_r \times_{K_{r-1}} K_r$ is isomorphic to

$$K_{r_1} \times_Y \cdots \times_Y K_{r_s} \times_Y K_1 \times_Y K_1.$$

We need to subdivide this case further: If $z = z'$, then the previous isomorphism takes ΔK_r to $K_{r_1} \times_Y \cdots \times_Y K_{r_s} \times_Y \Delta K_1$. In this case, the space K_{r+1} is locally isomorphic to

$$K_{r_1} \times_Y \cdots \times_Y K_{r_s} \times_Y K_2.$$

The map $K_{r+1} \rightarrow K_r$ is given by $K_2 \rightarrow K_1$ on the last component and leaves the other components untouched. This is an instance of case (2). If $z \neq z'$, then the diagonal ΔK_r does not intersect the open subset of $K_r \times_{K_{r-1}} K_r$ we are looking at, as long as the open neighborhoods U_i are small enough. In this case K_{r+1} is locally isomorphic to $K_r \times_{K_{r-1}} K_r$ and the map $K_{r+1} \rightarrow K_r$ drops the last component. This falls into case (1).

If K_r is of the form (1) around z and of the form (2) around z' , then $K_r \times_{K_{r-1}} K_r$ is isomorphic to

$$K_{r_1} \times_Y \cdots \times_Y K_{r_i+1} \times_Y \cdots \times_Y K_{r_s} \times_Y K_1,$$

and the first projection to K_r is given by $K_{r_i+1} \rightarrow K_{r_i}$ on the i th component. By hypothesis, this case occurs only for $z \neq z'$, hence K_{r+1} is locally isomorphic to $K_r \times_{K_{r-1}} K_r$ and we are in the case (2).

We leave to the reader to check the following cases: If K_r is of the form (2) around z and of the form (1) around z' , then we are in case (1). When K_r is of the form (2) around z and z' , we are in case (2).

Proof 5 (Lemma 4.4). We proceed by induction on s , skipping the case of $s = 2$, as it is analogous to the general case. Assume that the statement is true for $s - 1$. We may use the induction hypothesis and usual commutativities for fibered products to obtain the equality of the following compositions:

$$\begin{aligned} & ((K_{r+1}/K_r)^s \rightarrow (K_{r+1}/K_r)^{s-1} \rightarrow (K_r/K_{r-1})^s \rightarrow K_{r-1}) \\ &= \left((K_{r+1}/K_r)^s \rightarrow (K_{r+1}/K_r)^{s-1} \rightarrow (K_r/K_{r-1})^s \xrightarrow{\beta} K_r \rightarrow K_{r-1} \right) \\ &= \left((K_{r+1}/K_r)^s \rightarrow (K_{r+1}/K_r)^{s-1} \xrightarrow{\beta} K_{r+1} \rightarrow K_r \rightarrow K_{r-1} \right) \\ &= \left((K_{r+1}/K_r)^s \xrightarrow{\beta} K_{r+1} \rightarrow K_r \rightarrow K_{r-1} \right) \\ &= \left((K_{r+1}/K_r)^s \xrightarrow{\beta} K_{r+1} \xrightarrow{\tau} K_r \rightarrow K_{r-1} \right). \end{aligned}$$

This means that the two external paths in the hexagon below are equal. Therefore, by the universal property of $(K_r/K_{r-1})^{s+1}$, there exists a unique map $(K_{r+1}/K_r)^s \rightarrow (K_r/K_{r-1})^{s+1}$, satisfying the desired commutativities.

$$\begin{array}{ccc}
 (K_{r+1}/K_r)^s & \rightarrow & (K_{r+1}/K_r)^{s-1} \\
 \beta \downarrow & \searrow & \searrow \\
 & (K_r/K_{r-1})^{s+1} & \rightarrow & (K_r/K_{r-1})^s \\
 & \downarrow \beta & & \downarrow \\
 K_{r+1} & & & K_r & \longrightarrow & K_{r-1} \\
 & \searrow \tau & & & & \\
 & & & & &
 \end{array}$$

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

We are grateful to Steve Kleiman, for very helpful discussions during a stay of the second author in Boston. Grant PGC2018-094889-B-100 funded by MCIN/AEI/10.13039/501100011033 and by ‘ERDF A way of making Europe’.

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The *Journal of the London Mathematical Society* is wholly owned and managed by the London Mathematical Society, a not-for-profit Charity registered with the UK Charity Commission. All surplus income from its publishing programme is used to support mathematicians and mathematics research in the form of research grants, conference grants, prizes, initiatives for early career researchers and the promotion of mathematics.

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